

Closure Converting the Universes

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Abstract

Type preserving closure conversion of languages with dependent types has proved difficult. It took until 2018 to get the first solution to the problem, and that solution relies on language constructs custom-made for the purpose and does not support the customary tower of universes. There are basically three sources of difficulty. The first of them occurs when we need to close over variables which appear also in the type of the function, and can be solved with singleton types or translucent types. The second difficulty is the fact that closure conversion inevitably requires some form of impredicativity since a function can close over free variables that belong to a higher universe than itself. None of the existing forms of impredicativity (other than those known to be inconsistent) satisfy the needs of closure conversion with a tower of universes. And the last difficulty is that closure conversion exposes internal details of functions, and those details affect the definitional equality of (converted) functions, thereby breaking type preservation.

In this paper we investigate what is necessary to solve those three problems when implementing a type preserving closure conversion for a dependently typed λ -calculus with a tower of universes *without* relying on custom-made constructs in the target language, or more precisely while relying on constructs that are as generic as possible. Concretely, we use equality proofs to solve the first problem, a new form of impredicativity for the second, and quotient types for the third. While these functionalities were not custom-made for the purpose of closure conversion, we show how those high-level features need to be adjusted to accommodate a lower-level language where functions need to be closed.

1 Introduction

Closure conversion is a compilation stage that is a core part of the implementation of a functional programming language. We cannot compile a function like $\lambda x.x + a + b + c$ as-is into machine code because it contains data which is not known at compile-time: the values of a, b, c . Instead, compilers transform it into a so-called *closure* that may look like the following:

$$\langle \langle a, b, c \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x \rangle. \text{let } \langle a, b, c \rangle = x_e \text{ in } x + a + b + c \rangle$$

I.e. a pair of an *environment* $\langle a, b, c \rangle$ which captures the values of the free variables and a closed function $\lambda \langle x_e, x \rangle \dots$ which expects to receive this captured environment via an additional argument x_e . The closure conversion stage consists in rewriting the code to make explicit the creation and manipulation of those closure objects such that the remaining functions are all closed. Traditional compilation techniques can then turn those closed functions into raw machine code such that at run time, the $\lambda \langle x_e, x \rangle \dots$ part of a closure object is nothing more than a pointer to that machine code.

In the distant past, after type-checking the source code, compilers basically discarded the type information before passing the code through compilation stages like closure conversion. Nowadays, on the contrary, it is common for traditional functional languages to preserve the

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52 full type information across those compilation stages. While preserving types can have a
53 positive impact on the quality of the generated code [31, 34], the main benefit of preserving
54 the types across the various stages of the compiler is to ensure that the properties guaranteed
55 by the type checker apply not only to the source code but also to the corresponding compiled
56 code. This gets particularly important for dependently typed programming languages where
57 the programmers invest a lot of effort into embedded proofs in the source code.

58 Yet, preserving the full type information across this compilation stage is sadly not done
59 for dependently typed languages, for the simple reason that it stayed an open problem until
60 recently and the existing solutions are still not fully satisfactory. Instead, current compilers
61 for dependently typed programs end up discarding at least some of the type information along
62 the way because we do not know how to preserve it across all the compilation stages. As a
63 consequence, there is no way to check that two separately compiled pieces of code can be
64 linked without breaking any of their invariants, except in indirect ways, such as when they
65 were compiled with the same compiler and we still have access to their source code to check
66 their respective source types.
67

68 Preserving type information tends to get harder the further you progress in the compiler
69 pipeline. And dependent types make it a lot more difficult since run-time terms can appear
70 in the types: as the compilation stages modify those run-time terms, the typing information
71 tends to be affected in profound ways.
72

73 In the case of closure conversion, there are three main hurdles: the first is the need to
74 explain to the type system that the closure object we pass at run time to the closed code
75 indeed contains those precise values that were held in the free variables when we constructed
76 the closure (Section 3.1). The second is the fact that closure objects can contain not only
77 other closures of the same type, but also those closures' types, and hence their own type,
78 which means that the closure converted code requires some form of impredicativity even if
79 the source code was fully predicative (Section 3.2). The third is the fact that after closure
80 conversion, the variables captured by a closure are now in full view, at the meta-level, which
81 tends to completely change the notion of equality between functions and hence equality
82 between types (Section 3.3).
83

84 Bowman and Ahmed [8] provided a first, and so far only, solution to those three hurdles,
85 in order to preserve the types across the closure conversion stage of a dependently typed
86 language, but that solution still has two main shortcomings: first, it handles only the Calculus
87 of Constructions, which is an important but small subset of most dependently typed languages
88 used nowadays, so to be usable for an actual system it would need to be extended to cover
89 inductive types and a tower of universes. Second, it relies on a custom construct to represent
90 closures in the output language. While this is a very sensible pragmatic choice, it hides the
91 closures' concrete representation, thereby preventing further propagation of type information
92 into the lower-level code which manipulates the closures. Also it does beg the question: What
93 extra features would a language need in order to be able to accommodate closure converted
94 code without resorting to a custom construct?
95

96 In this article, we show an alternate path which makes different tradeoffs in order to find
97 a way to preserve the types across the closure conversion stage while sticking to generic
98 language constructs like dependent tuples and existential packages. Admittedly, our solution
99 still retains a few unusual characteristics, but gets closer to this ideal, and gives a possible
100 answer to the previous question.
101
102

Our contributions are the following:

- A type-preserving closure conversion algorithm for a dependently typed language with a tower of universes.
- A novel solution to the problem of aligning the definition of function equivalence in the code before and after closure conversion.
- A new impredicative typing rule for quantification over universe levels, to handle the need for impredicativity in the closure conversion algorithm.
- The use of equality proofs instead of the translucent types used by Minamide et al. [24]. This is admittedly already folklore at this point, and was also sketched by Bowman and Ahmed [8], but we are not aware of any previous work that shows the actual details.

This work suffers from a significant theoretical weakness in the form of an open question about the soundness of our target language and it may also prove impractical because of a somewhat burdensome encoding and a representation of closures that is not as efficient as that used by real compilers, but we believe it is an important step to understand better what are the requirements that a target language needs to satisfy for a type-preserving closure conversion to be possible and to motivate work towards satisfying those requirements. Another way to look at it is that exposing those weaknesses is also a contribution of this work: Why is it that even our best type systems are not able to validate the kind of code our compilers have been generating routinely for decades? Why can't we describe the workings of fully predicative functions without resorting to a brand new notion of impredicativity? Do (non-closed) functions make a type system stronger, in a proof-theoretical sense?

We present the basic problem of type-preserving closure conversion in Section 2. Section 3 presents each of the three difficulties facing closure conversion of dependently typed languages, along with an informal description of how we solved them. Section 4 shows more formally the input and output languages we use. Section 5 presents the closure conversion algorithm itself and possible extensions. Finally in Section 6 we discuss some of our design decisions.

2 Background

Let's consider a predicative Pure Type System (PTS) [2] with a tower of universes as our input language:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\text{levels}) \quad \ell & ::= 1 \mid S \ell \\
 (\text{sorts}) \quad s & ::= \mathcal{U}_\ell \\
 (\text{terms}) \quad e, \tau & ::= x \mid s \mid (e : \tau) \\
 & \quad \mid (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \mid e_1 e_2 \mid \lambda x. e
 \end{aligned}$$

Here \mathcal{U}_ℓ denotes the universe of level ℓ and we use $(x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2$ to denote the type of (dependent) functions, which we will shorten to $\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$ when x is not used in τ_2 . $(e : \tau)$ is a type annotation to help the bidirectional type checking, so that $\lambda x. e$ does not need a type annotation. $S \ell$ returns the successor of universe level ℓ and we use 1 as the base universe level here, because we will need to introduce a lower universe level later on.

Closure conversion needs to reify closures as data-structures usually represented using tuples, so our output language will additionally require some kind of tuples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\text{telescopes}) \quad \Gamma & ::= \bullet \mid \Gamma, x : \tau \\
 (\text{terms}) \quad e, \tau & ::= \dots \mid \langle \Gamma \rangle \mid \langle e_1, \dots, e_n \rangle \mid e.i
 \end{aligned}$$

154 $\langle \Gamma \rangle$ is the type constructor for (dependent) tuples, where Γ lists the types of the fields and
 155 where the type of later fields can refer to values of earlier fields; $\langle e_1, \dots, e_n \rangle$ is the tuple
 156 constructor; and $e.i$ returns the i^{th} field of the tuple e . For convenience we will use a bit of
 157 syntactic sugar and write: ¹

158 $\text{let } \langle x_1, \dots, x_n \rangle = e \text{ in } e'$ to mean $e'[e.1/x_1, \dots, e.n/x_n]$
 159 $\lambda \langle \vec{x} \rangle . e$ to mean $\lambda y. \text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = y \text{ in } e$ where \vec{x} stands for x_1, \dots, x_n
 160 $\langle x_1 : \tau_1, \dots, x_n : \tau_n \rangle \rightarrow \tau$ to mean $(x : \langle x_1 : \tau_1, \dots, x_n : \tau_n \rangle) \rightarrow \tau[x.1/x_1, \dots, x.n/x_n]$

162 Disregarding types for the moment, the closure conversion of a function like $f = \lambda x. x + y + z$
 163 may look like the following:

164
$$\llbracket \lambda x. x + y + z \rrbracket = \langle \langle y, z \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x \rangle . \text{let } \langle y, z \rangle = x_e \text{ in } x + y + z \rangle$$

167 This is a pair whose first element holds the *environment* $\langle y, z \rangle$ holding the values of the
 168 variables captured by the closure (y and z), and whose second element holds a closed function
 169 (the *code*). That function in turn expects as argument a pair $\langle x_e, x \rangle$ whose second element (x)
 170 is the actual argument to the function, and whose first element (x_e) should be the environment,
 171 holding the values of the captured variables, i.e. the first element of the closure.

172 Accordingly, after closure conversion, a call like $f\ 3$ would turn into:

173
$$\llbracket f\ 3 \rrbracket = \text{let } \langle f_e, f_c \rangle = f \text{ in } f_c \langle f_e, 3 \rangle$$

174 If we build the closure naïvely like we did above, its type would look like the following:

175
$$\langle \text{env} : \langle y : \text{Int}, z : \text{Int} \rangle, \text{code} : \langle x_e : \langle y : \text{Int}, z : \text{Int} \rangle, x : \text{Int} \rangle \rightarrow \text{Int} \rangle$$

177 But the type of this pair representing a function whose original type was $\text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int}$ now
 178 exposes the number and types of the captured variables. This implies that after closure
 179 conversion, two functions which originally had the same type can end up being represented
 180 by data structures of incompatible types, thus breaking the type preservation property. For
 181 this reason, closures are usually given an existential type that hides the type of the inner tuple
 182 representing the environment [24].

183 Since our tuples are dependently typed, we could use them for that, but we don't want that
 184 existentially quantified type to pollute our run-time values. So let's add the following syntax
 185 to our terms:

186
$$(\text{terms})\ e, \tau ::= \dots \mid \exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2 \mid \langle e_1; e_2 \rangle \mid \text{let } \langle x_1; x_2 \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$$

187 Here $\langle e_1; e_2 \rangle$ constructs an existential package, and the let binding in the open elimination
 188 rule will be constrained to make sure that we can always erase the first element of an existential
 189 package. With this new construct, we can now hide the type of the variables captured by our
 190 closure:

191
$$\llbracket \lambda x. x + y + z \rrbracket = \langle \langle y : \text{Int}, z : \text{Int} \rangle; \langle \langle y, z \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x \rangle . \text{let } \langle y, z \rangle = x_e \text{ in } x + y + z \rangle \rangle$$

 192
$$: \exists t : \mathcal{U}. \langle \text{env} : t, \text{code} : \langle x_e : t, x : \text{Int} \rangle \rightarrow \text{Int} \rangle$$

202 ¹Such syntactic sugar is not very practical in an implementation since it can increase code size significantly. It can
 203 be addressed by adding a proper let to our language, but we favored keeping the language small.

Now the type does not expose the shape of the captured environment, so two different functions that had the same type before conversion will still have the same type after conversion even if they capture a different number of variables or variables of different types.

This approach works well for System F [28], but when we try to apply it to a dependently typed language, three problems come up:

- (1) Some of the captured variables may also appear in the *type* of the function. In that case, our closure will be ill-typed because the type checker fails to see that the values extracted from x_e are the same as the ones that were captured.
- (2) The closure will tend to belong to too high a universe compared to the original function, because it contains the types of the captured variables.
- (3) The conversion does not preserve equivalence of terms. For example, when y is equal to 7, the above function is equivalent to $\lambda x.x + 7 + z$ but their respective closures will not be equivalent since they don't even have the same size: one captures two variables whereas the other captures only one. Since terms, like those functions, can appear in types, this means that types may also fail to be equivalent after closure conversion.

All three problems need to be solved if we want the closure conversion of properly typed code to still be properly typed.

3 Our approach

We present here in more detail the three mentioned problems that afflict type preserving closure conversion in the specific case of a dependently typed language, and we present informally the solution we used to solve each one.

3.1 Taming dependencies

The first problem we face was identified by Minamide et al. [24] already: if some of the free variables over which we close a function appear in its type, then the simple existential encoding fails. For example, say we have the following primitive:

$$\text{makevec} \quad : \quad (t : \mathcal{U}) \rightarrow (\text{len} : \text{Nat}) \rightarrow t \rightarrow \text{Vec } t \text{ len}$$

and we want to perform closure conversion on the following function:

$$\lambda x.\text{makevec } \alpha \ n \ x \quad : \quad \alpha \rightarrow \text{Vec } \alpha \ n$$

where α and n are its two free variables. The encoding shown before would give us:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \lambda x.\text{makevec } \alpha \ n \ x \rrbracket &= \langle \langle \alpha : \mathcal{U}, n : \text{Nat} \rangle; \\ &\quad \langle \langle \alpha, n \rangle, \\ &\quad \lambda \langle x_e, x \rangle.\text{let } \langle \alpha', n' \rangle = x_e \text{ in makevec } \alpha' \ n' \ x \rangle > \\ &: \exists t : \mathcal{U}.\langle \text{env} : t, \\ &\quad \text{code} : \langle x_e : t, x : \alpha \rangle \rightarrow \text{Vec } \alpha \ n \rangle \end{aligned}$$

But this code is ill-typed: Following the standard typing rules for existential types, dependent functions, and dependent tuples, in $\text{makevec } \alpha' \ n' \ x$, we tell makevec that we will provide an element of type α' but then pass it x which has type α . Also, even if we were generous enough to accept the argument x , the return type would not match the expected type because $\text{makevec } \alpha' \ n' \ x$ returns a value of type $\text{Vec } \alpha' \ n'$ rather than $\text{Vec } \alpha \ n$.

In the case of a language like System F, Morrisett et al. [28] showed that you can circumvent the problem by not closing over type variables, which are the only variables that can appear

in the type in such a language, and since types can be erased, we don't really need to close over them. In the above example, maybe α would not be used at run time and we could then leave it as a free variable, but that is not an option for n since that argument is needed at run time to determine the size of the returned vector.

Arguably the only value that x_e above can take is $\langle \alpha, n \rangle$ and thus α' will always be equal to α and n' will always be equal to n . With luck, you might even prove it via parametricity. Nevertheless, while *we* may know this, the type system does not. Worse, there is simply no way to write a closed function of the above type because in order to return something of type $\text{Vec } \alpha \ n$ it would have to refer to α and n , defeating the purpose of the closure conversion. For this reason, if we want the code to match its expected type, the type needs to make it more obvious that we will always receive in x_e the exact value stored in the *env* field of the tuple. Minamide et al. [24] did this using a feature called *translucent types* [17], and points out that singleton types can be used as well. We are not aware of any dependently typed language with native support for either translucent types or singleton types, so we opted instead to encode singleton types using equality proofs, which are ubiquitous in dependently typed languages:

$$(terms) \ e, \tau ::= \dots \mid e_1 = e_2 \mid \text{refl} \mid \text{cast}[e_m] \ e_ = e$$

$e_1 = e_2$ is the type of equality proofs between e_1 and e_2 , *refl* is the constructor of proofs that $e = e$, and *cast* is the eliminator which converts e from type $e_m \ e_1$ to type $e_m \ e_2$ when $e_ =$ is a proof that $e_1 = e_2$, where e_m is called the *motive* of the elimination. With that, we can fix our conversion:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \lambda x. \text{makevec } \alpha \ n \ x \rrbracket = & \langle \langle \alpha : \mathcal{U}, n : \text{Nat} \rangle; \\ & \langle \langle \alpha, n \rangle, \\ & \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. \text{let } \langle \alpha', n' \rangle = x_e \\ & \quad \text{in let } x' = \text{cast}[\lambda x'_e. x'_e. 1] \ (eq_comm \ p) \ x \\ & \quad \text{in let } res = \text{makevec } \alpha' \ n' \ x' \\ & \quad \text{in cast}[\lambda x'_e. \text{Vec } (x'_e. 1) \ (x'_e. 2)] \ p \ res \rangle \\ : & \exists t : \mathcal{U}. \langle env : t, \\ & \quad code : \langle x_e : t, x : \alpha, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rightarrow \text{Vec } \alpha \ n \rangle \end{aligned}$$

On the second line of the type we see that the *code* now takes an additional argument p holding a proof that $x_e = env$. Some readers at this point may be tempted to optimize away x_e since we know it's the same as env and refer directly to env instead, but that would defeat the purpose, since it would result in a non-closed λ -expression. The proof object p allows us to convert back and forth between the external types which refer to the surrounding variables and the internal types which refer only to variables local to the function. In the code, we see that p is passed a first time to *cast* (via *eq_comm*, which swaps the terms of the equality) in order to turn the input argument x of type α into x' of type $x_e. 1$ (which is also known here as α'), and then used a second time at the end to convert the result from $\text{Vec } (x_e. 1) \ (x_e. 2)$ (also known as $\text{Vec } \alpha' \ n'$) “back” to $\text{Vec } \alpha \ n$.

There is one wrinkle remaining here: this approach still would not quite work when the function to be converted is dependently typed. In the example above, the function $\lambda x'_e. \text{Vec } (x'_e. 1) \ (x'_e. 2)$ we pass as the motive of the second *cast* does not need to refer to the argument x , so all is well, but in the general case, the return type may refer to the argument x . But this function we use as motive cannot refer to x for two reasons: first, because it would then not be closed, but more importantly because the x it needs would be the actual x on one

side of the equality but x' on the other side. The usual solution to this problem is to merge both casts into one as follows:

```

307   let  $f' = \lambda x'. \text{makevec } \alpha' n' x'$ 
308   in let  $f = \text{cast}[\lambda x'_e. (x'_e.1) \rightarrow \text{Vec } (x'_e.1) (x'_e.2)] p f'$ 
309   in  $f x$ 

```

This is a variant of the *convoy pattern* [11]: in order to change the type of an expression at the same time as part of its context, we wrap this expression into a function taking the relevant part of its context as an argument (we named this function f' above), and once that function's type is changed (giving us the function f), we pass it the corresponding part of the context as argument.

But we cannot use this solution as-is because f' is not a closed function. The convoy pattern often relies crucially on non-closed functions, but we want to support it in our target language. For this reason, our target language replaces the `cast` operation with a `letcast` construct which includes the core element of the convoy pattern. It takes the following form:

$$\text{letcast}[e_m, e_ =] x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$$

It is equivalent to $(\text{cast}[e_m] e_ = (\lambda x. e_2)) e_1$ except that it avoids the temporary construction of a λ -expression, and thus turns into a plain `let` after type erasure.

3.2 Taming universes

In the previous section, we just used \mathcal{U} as the universe of types, but in the context of a language with a tower of universes, we need to qualify it with the corresponding level.

Let us consider the source function $g = \lambda x. 1 + f(x - 1)$, of type $\text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int}$. Its type after closure conversion becomes:

$$\llbracket \text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int} \rrbracket = \exists t : \mathcal{U}_\ell. \langle \text{env} : t, \text{code} : \langle x_e : t, x : \text{Int}, p : (x_e = \text{env}) \rangle \rightarrow \text{Int} \rangle$$

Here the ℓ subscript in \mathcal{U}_ℓ is the universe level inhabited by the captured environment. This existential type inhabits the universe $\mathcal{U}_{(S \ell)}$ since it contains a type $t : \mathcal{U}_\ell$. But when building the closure for $g = \lambda x. 1 + f(x - 1)$, the captured environment contains f which is also of type $\text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int}$ and whose type after closure conversion should thus also be the type above. So we would need to fit into the t field of the existential above an existential type belonging to $\mathcal{U}_{(S \ell)}$, which is clearly too large to fit into the \mathcal{U}_ℓ type of this field.

More specifically, we fundamentally need here some form of impredicativity such that our closure's existential quantification can quantify over a universe which includes its own. One solution is to use a language like λ^* that collapses all the universes into a single \mathcal{U} that belongs to itself, but those languages are known to be inconsistent [20]. All forms of impredicativity currently known to be consistent are too weak to accommodate our needs. Bowman and Ahmed [8] were the first to provide a solution to this problem by circumventing it and introducing a custom-made type construct for closures instead of relying on existential quantification.

While their solution only accommodates the Calculus of Constructions, it might be possible to adapt it to a language with a tower of universes. Yet, we would prefer a solution that does not rely on such custom constructs. Going back to the tuple type above, we can see another problem with it: the universe level ℓ needed for the field t of the tuple depends on the types

358 of captured variables, and hence leaks details of the captured variables. As in Sec. 2, we face
 359 the problem that the closure conversion of two different closures of the same original type
 360 may end up having different types depending on the set of captured variables, thus breaking
 361 again our dear type preservation property.

362 So we apply the same existential quantification trick, but this time quantifying over the
 363 universe level:
 364

$$365 \quad \llbracket \text{Int} \rightarrow \text{Int} \rrbracket = \exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle \text{env} : t, \\ 366 \quad \text{code} : \langle x_e : t, x : \text{Int}, p : (x_e = \text{env}) \rangle \rightarrow \text{Int} \rangle$$

368 We assume here that this new existential construct $\exists l. \tau$ is the natural generalization to
 369 universe levels of the usual existential quantification. We will want to keep it separate from
 370 the previous $\exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2$ because manipulating universe levels as first class values is fraught
 371 with danger.

372 We will want to make sure that universe levels can be erased, so we do not need to close
 373 over them, saving us from the kind of extra complications we saw in Section 3.1, such as the
 374 need to manipulate proofs of equality between universe levels. The introduction of universe
 375 level variables l is accompanied with a new construct $\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2$ which represents the max
 376 operation on levels.
 377

378 With this extra existential quantification, we recover the property that the converted type
 379 of a function is always the same regardless of its free variables. But there still remains the
 380 question of the universe to which this type should belong. Some languages, such as Agda,
 381 support this kind of existential (and universal) quantification over universe levels [5, 10],
 382 but they use a predicative typing rule for it which puts it in a universe level beyond all the
 383 levels over which it quantifies (e.g. Agda uses a special universe ω). This of course would not
 384 satisfy our impredicative needs.
 385

386 A naïve impredicative choice would put this type in the bottom universe instead, but this
 387 would immediately lead to an inconsistent type theory because we could then use dummy
 388 $\exists l. \tau$ wrappers to bring any type down to the bottom universe, making the language equivalent
 389 to λ^* .

390 Taking a step back, we can let the needs of the closure converted code guide our choice of
 391 the universe in which we place a type of the form $\exists l. \tau$:

- 392 • Let us take a source function type $(x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 : \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2}$, where $\tau_1 : \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1}$ and
 393 $\tau_2 : \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2}$.
- 394 • In order for our closure conversion to preserve types, we need
 395 $\llbracket (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket : \llbracket \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2} \rrbracket$. Similarly, we need:
 396 – $\llbracket \mathcal{U}_\ell \rrbracket = \mathcal{U}_{\llbracket \ell \rrbracket}$ because the encoding of a type needs itself to be a type.
 397 – $\llbracket S \ell \rrbracket = S \llbracket \ell \rrbracket$, because given that $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{U}_\ell : \mathcal{U}_{(S \ell)}$, we need
 398 $\Gamma \vdash \llbracket \mathcal{U}_\ell \rrbracket : \llbracket \mathcal{U}_{(S \ell)} \rrbracket$, which means $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{U}_{\llbracket \ell \rrbracket} : \mathcal{U}_{\llbracket S \ell \rrbracket}$.
 399 – $\llbracket \ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2 \rrbracket = \llbracket \ell_1 \rrbracket \sqcup \llbracket \ell_2 \rrbracket$ because we need to preserve the stratification: if
 400 $\ell_a < \ell_b$ then we need $\llbracket \ell_a \rrbracket < \llbracket \ell_b \rrbracket$.
- 401 • $\llbracket (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket$ is $\exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle \text{env} : t, \text{code} : \langle x_e : t, x : \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket \rrbracket, p : (x_e = \text{env}) \rangle \rightarrow \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket \rangle$.
- 402 • Since $\llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket : \mathcal{U}_{\llbracket \ell_1 \rrbracket}$ and $\llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket : \mathcal{U}_{\llbracket \ell_2 \rrbracket}$ and the rest fits into $\mathcal{U}_{S l}$, the inner \exists has type
 403 $\mathcal{U}_{(\llbracket \ell_1 \rrbracket \sqcup \llbracket \ell_2 \rrbracket \sqcup S l)}$.
- 404 • So our closure conversion requires that given a type $\tau : \mathcal{U}_{(\llbracket \ell_1 \rrbracket \sqcup \llbracket \ell_2 \rrbracket \sqcup S l)}$, we must
 405 have $\exists l. \tau : \mathcal{U}_{\llbracket \ell_1 \rrbracket \sqcup \llbracket \ell_2 \rrbracket}$. To eliminate that $\sqcup l$ we can try making l at least as small
 406
 407
 408

as either $\llbracket \ell_1 \rrbracket$ or $\llbracket \ell_2 \rrbracket$. One way to do that is to substitute l with a new universe 0 that sits beneath all the others.

We adopt the rule that $\exists l.\tau$ is given type $\mathcal{U}_{\ell[0/l]}$ when τ has type \mathcal{U}_ℓ . Whether this choice is sound is currently unknown: impredicativity is notoriously dangerous and this particular form of impredicativity has not been investigated to any significant extent. We discuss in more details the impact of this rule in Sec. 6.5.

3.3 Taming function equality

The final remaining problem is the preservation of equality for functions: for the closure conversion to preserve types, we also need to make sure that closure conversion preserves equality between types, and since types can contain arbitrary terms, we need to preserve equality between terms, i.e. if $e_1 \simeq e_2$ then $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \simeq \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket$.

But this is not the case with our current encoding: in our source language $e_1 = \lambda x.x + 7$ is equivalent to $e_2 = \text{let } y = 7 \text{ in } \lambda x.x + y$ because e_2 reduces to e_1 . But after closure conversion, these two terms are not equivalent any more. The first will be a closure capturing an empty environment:

$$\begin{aligned} & \llbracket \lambda x.x + 7 \rrbracket \\ & = \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle . x + 7 \rangle \rangle \end{aligned}$$

While the second will be a closure capturing an environment containing the value of y :

$$\begin{aligned} & \llbracket \text{let } y = 7 \text{ in } \lambda x.x + y \rrbracket \\ & = \text{let } y = 7 \text{ in } \langle 1; \langle y : \text{Int} \rangle; \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle . x + x_e.1 \rangle \rangle \\ & \sim \\ & \langle 1; \langle y : \text{Int} \rangle; \langle \langle 7 \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle . x + x_e.1 \rangle \rangle \end{aligned}$$

These two closures are clearly not definitionally equal and it is difficult to adjust our language's reduction rules so as to allow them to treat those two objects as equivalent. The custom-made closure construct used by Bowman and Ahmed [8] to circumvent the problem of impredicativity saves them again here, since it allows them to provide a specific η -equivalence rule for those objects. But with our use of tuples, our hands are tied.

With an appropriate model, we could try to leverage parametricity to justify an ad-hoc η -equivalence theorem for our closure objects, as done by Bowman [7], but since we don't have such a model, we decided instead to use quotient types, which do not depend so heavily on meta-theoretical properties of our language.

Although support for quotient types in programming languages goes back at least to the first version of Miranda [36, 37], they are not nearly as common as existentials, tuples, and equality proofs. There are different ways to add quotient types to a language, but to a first approximation we can classify them into two groups: those which define a quotient via a relation (and hence correspond most closely to the traditional mathematical presentation) such as higher inductive types [35], and those which define a quotient via a normalization function that takes elements to their equivalence class [13].² While the use of relations is more general and arguably more standard, we opted to use quotient types based on normalization functions, because in exchange for the ability to define such a normalization function (which, luckily, we have), they provide a stronger definitional equality. This significantly simplifies

²With various options trying to provide a mix of the two, see for instance the quotient library by Cohen [12], or the Arend proof assistant.

our proof of type preservation because definitional equality is thus also preserved by the conversion. More specifically, we add the following terms to our syntax:

$$(terms) \ e, \tau ::= \dots \mid \mathbb{Q} \ e_n \mid \mathbb{Q}in[e_n] \ e \mid \text{let}[e_=] \ \mathbb{Q}in \ x = e_1 \ \text{in} \ e_2$$

Where $\mathbb{Q} \ e_n$ is the quotient type defined by the normalization function e_n of type $\tau \rightarrow \tau$, where τ is the type that is quotiented by e_n ; $\mathbb{Q}in[e_n] \ e$ is the constructor which projects values of type τ into $\mathbb{Q} \ e_n$; and $\text{let}[e_=] \ \mathbb{Q}in \ x = e_1 \ \text{in} \ e_2$ is the elimination form where $e_=$ is the proof that we obey the quotient's equality, i.e. a proof that $e_2 \simeq e_2[e_n \ x/x]$. There is no dedicated introduction form for equality between quotiented values, because instead we strengthen the definitional equality so $\mathbb{Q}in[e_n] \ e_1 \simeq \mathbb{Q}in[e_n] \ e_2$ when $e_n \ e_1 \simeq e_n \ e_2$.

So we can now quotient the encoding of our closures with a normalization function. We choose as canonical representative of each equivalence class the closure object where the captured environment is empty. These representative closure objects have the property that their *code* is in general not closed any more, and indeed they amount, in a sense, to turning the closures back into their non-closed form, thereby recovering the original equality semantics:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{clotype } \tau_1 \ x. \tau_2 &= \exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle env : t, \\ &\quad code : \langle x_e : t, x : \tau_1, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rightarrow \tau_2 \rangle \\ \llbracket \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket & \\ &= \mathbb{Q} \ (\lambda \langle l; \langle t; \langle env, code \rangle \rangle. \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. code \ \langle env, x, refl \rangle \rangle \rangle) \\ &\quad : \text{clotype } \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket \ x. \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket \rightarrow \text{clotype } \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket \ x. \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket \end{aligned}$$

When we want to call a closure, we need to use the elimination form of the quotient $\text{let}[e_=] \ \mathbb{Q}in \ x = e_1 \ \text{in} \ e_2$ to which we have to provide the proof $e_=$ that we obey the quotient's equality. For our uses, this proof is simple since e_2 is the code that calls the closure and it is very similar to the code of the normalization function.

When adding quotient types using axioms, the quotient eliminator is typically defined to take the quotiented object and a function representing the body of our *let* construct, but of course, this would not work here because that function would usually not be closed. In other words, our eliminator takes the shape of a *let* for the same reason we introduced *letcast*. This is a common theme when working in a lower-level intermediate language.

3.4 Taming closedness

One more issue that keeps popping up is what exactly we should consider as “closed”: given a source function $\lambda x. x \ y$, it is natural to consider that we should make a closure that captures y and nothing else, but after closure conversion the code will usually want to refer to the types of both x and y , for example in the motives of the casts.

Also, dependencies can get in the way. Let's say we have a source function $\lambda x. insert \ t \ x \ s$ with a typing environment that contains $\{\dots, t : \mathcal{U}_1, o : Ordering \ t, s : BinarySet \ t \ o, \dots\}$. If we close over t and s but not over o , the closed code will not be properly typed because the type of s will be ill-formed since it will not refer to the same t as the type of o any more. For this reason, we need to transitively close over all the variables that appear in the types of the free variables (as well as the type of the function itself).

More problematic yet: in the previous section, the quotient's normalization function includes the non-closed function $\lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. code \ \langle env, x, refl \rangle$. We cannot easily close this function without reintroducing the problem it's trying to address, nor can we hide it via some kind of *let*-like construct.

511 $\boxed{e_1 \simeq e_2}$ e_1 is definitionally equal to e_2 :
 512 $\boxed{e_1 \rightsquigarrow e_2}$ e_1 reduces to e_2 :
 513
 514
$$\llbracket (e : \tau) \rrbracket \rightsquigarrow e \quad ((\lambda x. e_1) : (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \rightsquigarrow (e_1 : \tau_2) \llbracket (e_2 : \tau_1) / x \rrbracket$$

 515
 516
$$\frac{e_1 \rightsquigarrow^* e_3 \quad e_2 \rightsquigarrow^* e_3}{e_1 \simeq e_2}$$

 517
 518

Fig. 1. Convertibility rules of our source language.

522 $\boxed{\Gamma \vdash N \Rightarrow \tau}$ and $\boxed{\Gamma \vdash M \Leftarrow \tau}$ The form has type τ in context Γ :
 523

524
 525
$$\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{U}_\ell \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{(S \ell)} \text{ (SORT)} \quad \frac{\tau_1 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_2 \quad \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_1} \text{ (RED}_C\text{)}$$

 526
 527
 528
$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_1 \quad \tau_1 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_2} \text{ (RED}_S\text{)} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash N \Rightarrow \tau_1 \quad \tau_1 \simeq \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash \llbracket N \rrbracket \Leftarrow \tau_2} \text{ (CONV)}$$

 529
 530
 531
 532
$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s \quad \Gamma \vdash M \Leftarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash (M : \tau) \Rightarrow \tau} \text{ (ANN)}$$

 533
 534
 535
$$\frac{\Gamma(x) = \tau}{\Gamma \vdash x \Rightarrow \tau} \text{ (VAR)}$$

 536
 537
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$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1} \quad \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2} \quad \ell_3 = \max(\ell_1, \ell_2)}{\Gamma \vdash (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_3}} \text{ (PI)}$$

 540
 541
 542
$$\frac{\Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x. e \Leftarrow ((x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2)} \text{ (LAM)} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Rightarrow (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2 \Leftarrow \tau_1}{\Gamma \vdash e_1 e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2 \llbracket (e_2 : \tau_1) / x \rrbracket} \text{ (APP)}$$

 543
 544
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Fig. 2. Typing rules of the source language.

550 Luckily, those normalization functions are used only during type checking but are erased
 551 along with type annotations before generating the machine code. So we need to refine what
 552 we mean by closed. We need to distinguish those elements needed only for typing purposes
 553 from those needed at run time: our closure conversion does not require that all λ -expressions
 554 be closed in the closure-converted code, but only that all λ -expressions be closed after type
 555 erasure. This is because only the code after type erasure will be executed at run time and thus
 556 needs to be compilable to machine code.
 557

558 4 Languages

560 In this section we define the source and target languages for our closure conversion.
 561

4.1 Source language

The source language we intend to convert has the following syntax:

(levels)	ℓ	$::=$	$S\ 0 \mid S\ \ell$
(sorts)	s	$::=$	\mathcal{U}_ℓ
(syn terms)	e, τ, N	$::=$	$x \mid s \mid (M : \tau) \mid (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \mid N\ M$
(chk terms)	e, M	$::=$	$[N] \mid \lambda x.M$

This is the same language as shown at the beginning of Section 2, except that the bottom universe level 1 is now spelled $S\ 0$ and terms are split into the terms we call *syn* terms, for which types can be synthesized, and *chk* terms, for which types can be only checked. We still use e in most places except when this distinction is important, and we use τ for terms that are intended to denote types. $[\cdot]$ allows the use of a synthesizing term in a checking context, but we will usually omit it since we can almost always infer its presence from the context. The use of $S\ 0$ instead of 1 or 0 for the bottom universe is there solely as a convenience to keep the universe levels of the source language aligned with those of the target language where we will need an additional “basement” universe 0.

The convertibility rules $e_1 \simeq e_2$ and $e_1 \rightsquigarrow e_2$ are shown in Figure 1, where E stand for any program context. The rules are untyped but defined such that if input expressions are properly typed in the same context, then all the terms used along the way are themselves properly typed. To that end, $e_1 \simeq e_2$ is defined on top of \rightsquigarrow^* which is the transitive reflexive closure of small step reduction rule \rightsquigarrow . The only typing rule which uses the convertibility rule, i.e. the CONV rule, indeed guarantees that τ_1 and τ_2 are well formed in the same context, so in practice we will always invoke $e_1 \simeq e_2$ with well-formed terms. Similarly we only ever use $e_1 \rightsquigarrow e_2$ with a well typed e_1 .

The typing rules for this source language are shown in Figure 2. We show them in a bidirectional style [14] to try and reduce the type annotations in our code. The main judgment is split between $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ and $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$ where the first synthesizes the type τ from the context Γ and the term e whereas the second just checks it. The rules presume that Γ in the conclusion is well-formed, as is the type passed to the \Leftarrow rule. We will sometimes use $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$ to mean that it can be either $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ or $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$. The two RED rules allow arbitrary reductions between typing steps, but they only ever need to reduce to weak-head normal form. Our calculus does not use universe subsumption, which is why in the PI rule, we allow input and output types from different universes. Notice also that the source language does not include level variables and associated \sqcup operator, which will appear only in the target language.

Beside the details of presentation of conversion and type checking, this is a conventional dependently typed λ -calculus with a predicative tower of universes and without universe subsumption. It enjoys a lot of nice meta-theoretical properties, such as confluence and subject reduction.

LEMMA 1 (CONFLUENCE).

If $e \rightsquigarrow e_l$ and $e \rightsquigarrow e_r$, then there exists an e_m such that $e_l \rightsquigarrow e_m$ and $e_r \rightsquigarrow e_m$.

PROOF. By the usual Tait/Martin-Löf method. See also the the proof of the corresponding Lemma 3 for the target language. \square

613	(levels)	ℓ	$::= l \mid 0 \mid S \ell \mid \ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2$	
614	(sorts)	s	$::= \mathcal{U}_\ell$	
615	(index)	i	$\in \mathbb{N}^*$	Positions in tuples
616	(ctx)	Γ	$::= \bullet \mid \Gamma, x : \tau$	
617	(syn terms)	e, τ, N	$::= x \mid s$	Variables and sorts
618			$\mid (M : \tau)$	Type annotation
619			$\mid (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2$	Function type
620			$\mid N M$	Function application
621			$\mid \langle \Gamma \rangle$	Dependent tuple type
622			$\mid N.i$	i^{th} projection from a tuple
623			$\mid \exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2$	Existential type
624			$\mid \text{let } \langle x_1; x_2 \rangle = N_1 \text{ in } N_2$	Existential eliminator
625			$\mid \exists l. \tau$	Existential universe type
626			$\mid \text{let } \langle l; x \rangle = N_1 \text{ in } N_2$	Existential universe eliminator
627			$\mid \text{Eq } N M$	Equality type
628			$\mid \text{letcast}[N_m, N_ =] x = N \text{ in } M$	Eliminator of equality type
629			$\mid Q N$	Quotient type
630			$\mid \text{let}[M_ =] Q \text{ in } x = N_1 \text{ in } N_2$	Quotient eliminator
631			$\mid Q \text{ in } [N_n] N$	Main constructor of quotient
632			$\mid Q \text{ n } [N_n] N$	Extra constructor of quotient
633	(chk terms)	e, M	$::= [N]$	Syn term
634			$\mid \lambda x. M$	Function constructor
635			$\mid \langle M_1, \dots, M_n \rangle$	Tuple constructor
636			$\mid \langle M_1; M_2 \rangle$	Existential constructor
637			$\mid \langle \ell; M \rangle$	Existential universe constructor
638			$\mid \text{refl}$	Equality constructor
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Fig. 3. Syntax of the target language

LEMMA 2 (SUBJECT REDUCTION).

Given $e \rightsquigarrow e'$, if $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma \vdash e' \Leftarrow \tau$,
and if $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma \vdash e' \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'$.

PROOF. By induction on $e \rightsquigarrow e'$ and the typing derivation of e . It is a subset of the proof of the corresponding Lemma 7 for the target language. \square

4.2 Target language

Our target language is a superset of our source language. Its syntax is given in Figure 3. The quantification over universe levels adds two new elements to the syntax of levels ℓ : one for level variables l , and another for the maximum of two levels $\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2$. The language includes a notion of type erasure denoted $|e|$ (whose own target language will be shown later in Figure 10) that we use mainly to clarify the intended run-time semantics but which appears also in the typing rules.

The sorts and contexts stay unchanged, but we add many new elements to the terms:

$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1} \quad \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2}}{\Gamma \vdash (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{(\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2)}} \text{ (P1)}$ $0 \sqcup \ell \rightsquigarrow \ell \quad \ell \sqcup 0 \rightsquigarrow \ell$ $(S \ell_1) \sqcup (S \ell_2) \rightsquigarrow S (\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2)$	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block; margin-bottom: 5px;"> e </div> Type erasure of e : <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr><td>x</td><td>$= x$</td></tr> <tr><td>$\mathcal{U}\ell$</td><td>$= \mathcal{U}$</td></tr> <tr><td>$(e : \tau)$</td><td>$= e$</td></tr> <tr><td>$(x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2$</td><td>$= \rightarrow$</td></tr> <tr><td>$e_1 e_2$</td><td>$= e_1 e_2$</td></tr> <tr><td>$\lambda x. e$</td><td>$= \lambda x. e$</td></tr> </table>	$ x $	$= x$	$ \mathcal{U}\ell $	$= \mathcal{U}$	$ (e : \tau) $	$= e $	$ (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 $	$= \rightarrow$	$ e_1 e_2 $	$= e_1 e_2 $	$ \lambda x. e $	$= \lambda x. e $
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$ e_1 e_2 $	$= e_1 e_2 $												
$ \lambda x. e $	$= \lambda x. e $												

Fig. 4. Differences with source language for the core target language.

- Dependent tuples: $\langle \Gamma \rangle$ is the type of dependent tuples where Γ describes the fields and their types; $\langle e_1, \dots, e_n \rangle$ is the corresponding term constructor; and $e.i$ is the elimination form which projects the i^{th} field out of e .
- Existential types: $\exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2$ is the existential type that quantifies over x ; $\langle e_1; e_2 \rangle$ is the corresponding constructor, where e_1 is erasable; and $\text{let } \langle x_1; x_2 \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$ is its elimination form, where x_1 can be used only in erasable code.
- Existential universe types: $\exists l. \tau$ is the existential type that quantifies over universe level l ; $\langle l; e \rangle$ is the corresponding constructor; and $\text{let } \langle l; x \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$ is its elimination form.
- Equality types: $\text{Eq } e_1 e_2$ is the type of proofs that e_1 and e_2 are equal; refl is the corresponding constructor of the proof by reflexivity; and $\text{letcast}[e_m, e_=_] x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$ is the elimination form which takes a proof $e_=_ : \text{Eq } e_i e_o$ and a motive e_m , and behaves like $\text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$. The motive e_m is a type annotation in the form of a function: $e_m e_i$ should return a type of the form $(x : \tau_{i1}) \rightarrow \tau_{i2}$ where τ_{i1} is the type of x and τ_{i2} is the type of e_2 ; and $e_m e_o$ should return a type of the form $(x : \tau_{o1}) \rightarrow \tau_{o2}$ where τ_{o1} is the type of e_1 and τ_{o2} is the type of the overall letcast expression.
- Quotient types: $\mathbb{Q} e$ is the quotient type where e is the normalization function; $\text{Qin}[e_n] e$ is its main constructor where e_n is again the normalization function; and $\text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$ is its elimination form where $e_=_$ is the proof that it obeys the quotient's equality. We follow the design of *normalizable types* [25] and thus need a secondary constructor $\text{Qn}[e_n] e$ used only internally in the typing and reduction rules to keep track of the fact that e has already been normalized.

As is customary for bidirectional typing, all the types and eliminators are syn terms, and most of the constructors are chk terms. Qin is nevertheless an exception to this rule: we could make it a chk term of the form $\text{Qin } e$ and determine e_n from its expected return type, but we need e_n in the reduction rules of Qin , so we opted to include e_n in the syntax $\text{Qin}[e_n] e$ in order to avoid the need for a typed conversion rule. The same argument does not apply to Qn , but we kept it as a syn term simply to minimize the difference with Qin .

Since our target language is a superset of our source language, the core elements are the same and basically share the same rules, except for changes to the universe levels. Figure 4 shows the parts of the rules that changed, fundamentally due to the fact that the $\max(\ell_1, \ell_2)$ computation that used to be performed at the metalevel is now internalized as $\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2$, which in turn requires new conversion rules to define the semantics of this operation. Another

$$\begin{array}{l}
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717 \quad (\text{terms}) \quad e, \tau ::= \dots \mid \langle \Gamma \rangle \mid \langle e_1, \dots, e_n \rangle \mid e.i \\
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720 \quad \Gamma \vdash \langle \bullet \rangle \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_1 \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \langle \Gamma' \rangle \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1} \quad \Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash \tau \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2}}{\Gamma \vdash \langle \Gamma', x : \tau \rangle \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2}} (\Sigma) \\
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723 \quad \Gamma \vdash \langle \rangle \Leftarrow \langle \bullet \rangle \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \langle \vec{e} \rangle \Leftarrow \langle \Gamma' \rangle \quad \Gamma' = \vec{x} : \vec{\tau} \quad \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau[\vec{e}/\vec{x}]}{\Gamma \vdash \langle \vec{e}, e \rangle \Leftarrow \langle \Gamma', x : \tau \rangle} (\text{TUP}) \\
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726 \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \langle \Gamma' \rangle \quad \Gamma' = \vec{x} : \vec{\tau}}{\Gamma \vdash e.i \Rightarrow \tau_i[e.1/x_1, \dots, e.(i-1)/x_{i-1}]} (\text{PROJ}) \\
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730 \quad ((\vec{e}) : \langle \vec{x} : \vec{\tau} \rangle).i \rightsquigarrow (e_i : \tau_i[(e_1 : \tau_1)/x_1, \dots, (e_{i-1} : \tau_{i-1})/x_{i-1}]) \\
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Fig. 5. Dependent tuples.

change is the fact that the base universe level is now really called 0, so it sits one level below the base universe of the source language.

In addition to those changes, the target language has a notion of type erasure denoted $|e|$ whose definition for the base elements of the language is shown in that same figure, where we can see that it simply traverses the terms and removes the explicit type annotations and the universe levels. Its effect on type constructors is of no importance since there are no operations on types performed at run time, so we pick arbitrary inert constants for them. Its effects on other constructs is presented in the following subsections.

4.2.1 Dependent tuples

Figure 5 shows the rules governing the dependent tuples, which subsume sigma types. There is nothing novel here. The main complexity lies in the rules PROJ and TUP which need to take into account the possible dependencies between the fields, which requires applying substitutions to replace references to previous fields with those fields' values when returning the type of fields. Notice also the Σ rule which computes the maximum level of universe in the tuples' members in order to decide in which universe to put the tuple type.

4.2.2 Existential types

Figure 6 shows the rules that govern existential types. The first thing to note here is in the top right corner, after the rule that erases the type constructor to a dummy \exists , we see that type erasure throws away the left hand side of those existential packages. For this to make sense, the OPEN rule makes sure the x_1 variable is not used in a way that is computationally relevant, by enforcing that it does not occur as a free variable in the *type erasure* of the body of the let. This is the only place where the type erasure is used in the typing rules.

In most other respects, this is a simplified version of the rules we use for dependent tuples, where the simplification comes from the fact that we only handle pairs here, instead of an arbitrary number of elements, and the fact that the elimination rule does not allow the return type to depend on the pair. Regarding this OPEN rule, the $\Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s$ premise may seem

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\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
| \exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2 | = \exists \\
| \langle e_1; e_2 \rangle | = | e_2 | \\
| \text{let } \langle x_1; x_2 \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 | \\
= \text{let } x_2 = | e_1 | \text{ in } | e_2 |
\end{array}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1} \quad \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2}}{\Gamma \vdash \exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2}} (\exists)$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Leftarrow \tau_1 \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2 \Leftarrow \tau_2[(e_1 : \tau_1)/x]}{\Gamma \vdash \langle e_1; e_2 \rangle \Leftarrow \exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2} (\text{PACK})$$

$$\frac{x_1 \notin \text{fv}(|e_2|) \quad \Gamma, x_1 : \tau_1, x_2 : \tau_2 \vdash e_2 \Rightarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s}{\Gamma \vdash \text{let } \langle x_1; x_2 \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Rightarrow \tau} (\text{OPEN})$$

$$\text{let } \langle x_1; x_2 \rangle = \langle e_1; e_2 \rangle : \exists x_1 : \tau_1. \tau_2 \text{ in } e_b \rightsquigarrow e_b[(e_1 : \tau_1)/x_1, (e_2 : \tau_2[(e_1 : \tau_1)/x_1])/x_2]$$

Fig. 6. Existential types.

redundant since we already know that τ is a well-formed type and we don't use s elsewhere, but its purpose is to verify that τ is closed w.r.t. x_1 and x_2 .

These rules can be seen as a subset of those proposed by Bernardo [4] for the Σ type of ICC_Σ^* . Our $\exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2$ corresponds in that work to $\Sigma[x : \tau_1]. \tau_2$, i.e. a pair whose first field is erased, except that we use a weaker rule for the eliminator: the eliminator for ICC_Σ^* is dependent, in the sense that it allows the return type to depend on the pair, whereas we use a simpler non-dependent eliminator. They use the same side-condition of $x_1 \notin \text{fv}(|e_2|)$ to enforce that the witness is computationally irrelevant.

4.2.3 Existential universe types

Figure 7 shows the rules that govern existential quantification over universe levels. We see that the type erasure for existential universe types follow basically the same rules as for existential types. But note that U-OPEN does not need to check that l is not used in the erasure of e_2 because we know it by construction: erasure erases all universe level annotations anyway.

Our typing judgment does not include any context listing the set of universe level variables l that are currently in scope. There is no deep technical reason for that, we simply decided to go for a presentation that does without it, as is done sometimes for the set of type variables in System F. This saves us from having to carry around another context in all the typing rules, but it requires extra care in the typing rules to avoid variable captures since we cannot rely on the usual Barendregt convention. This manifests itself in the tests that l is not free in Γ or τ in the U- \exists and U-OPEN rules. More importantly we see in the U- \exists rule the crucial impredicativity where we return the type $\mathcal{U}_{\ell_{[0/l]}}$, which corresponds to the infimum $\inf_l \ell$ whereas the traditional predicative choice would be to use the supremum $\sup_l \ell$ which would result in something like \mathcal{U}_ω , as used in Agda. This is the only part of our target language that

$$\begin{array}{l}
868 \\
869 \quad (terms) \quad e, \tau ::= \dots \mid \text{Eq } e_1 e_2 \mid \text{refl} \\
870 \quad \quad \quad \mid \text{letcast}[e_m, e_=_] x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \\
871 \\
872 \\
873 \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Rightarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2 \Leftarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s}{\Gamma \vdash \text{Eq } e_1 e_2 \Rightarrow s} \text{(EQ)} \quad \frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \text{refl} \Leftarrow \text{Eq } e e} \text{(REFL)} \\
874 \\
875 \\
876 \\
877 \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_=_ \Rightarrow \text{Eq } e_1 e_2 \quad \Gamma \vdash e_m e_1 \Rightarrow s \quad e_m e_1 \rightsquigarrow^* (x:\tau_{a1}) \rightarrow \tau_{r1} \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_{a1} \vdash e_r \Leftarrow \tau_{r1}}{\Gamma \vdash \text{letcast}[e_m, e_=_] x = e_a \text{ in } e_r \Rightarrow \tau_{r2}[e_a/x]} \\
878 \quad \quad \quad e_m e_2 \rightsquigarrow^* (x:\tau_{a2}) \rightarrow \tau_{r2} \quad \Gamma \vdash e_a \Leftarrow \tau_{a2} \\
879 \\
880 \\
881 \quad \frac{e_m e_1 \rightsquigarrow^* (x:\tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r}{\text{letcast}[e_m, (\text{refl} : \text{Eq } e_1 e_2)] x = e_a \text{ in } e_r \rightsquigarrow (e_r : \tau_r)[e_a/x]} \\
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\end{array}$$

Fig. 8. Typing rules for the identity type.

$$\begin{array}{l}
889 \\
890 \quad (terms) \quad e, \tau ::= \dots \mid \text{Q } e_n \mid \text{Qin}[e_n] e_v \mid \text{Qn}[e_n] e_v \\
891 \quad \quad \quad \mid \text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \\
892 \\
893 \quad \quad \quad \mid \text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \\
894 \quad \quad \quad \quad = \text{let } x = |e_1| \text{ in } |e_2| \\
895 \\
896 \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_n \Rightarrow \tau \rightarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s}{\Gamma \vdash \text{Q } e_n \Rightarrow s} \text{(Q)} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_n \Rightarrow \tau \rightarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash e_v \Leftarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash \text{Qin}[e_n] e_v \Rightarrow \text{Q } e_n} \text{(QIN)} \\
897 \\
898 \\
899 \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_n \Rightarrow \tau \rightarrow \tau \quad \Gamma \vdash e_v \Leftarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash \text{Qn}[e_n] e_v \Rightarrow \text{Q } e_n} \text{(QN)} \\
900 \\
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902 \\
903 \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Rightarrow \text{Q } e_n \quad \Gamma \vdash e_n \Rightarrow \tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_1 \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_1 \vdash e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2 \quad \Gamma, x:\tau_1 \vdash e_=_ \Leftarrow \text{Eq } e_2 (e_2[e_n x/x])}{\Gamma \vdash \text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2} \text{(QOUT)} \\
904 \\
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906 \\
907 \quad \text{Qin}[e_n] e \rightsquigarrow \text{Qn}[e_n] (e_n e) \quad \text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = \text{Qn}[e_n] e_v \text{ in } e_b \rightsquigarrow e_b[e_v/x] \\
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\end{array}$$

Fig. 9. Quotient types.

type annotation in the result. Since the reduction rules are actually untyped, an implementation could arguably strip all type annotations while performing conversion checks.

More importantly, we see in the erasure rules that the `letcast` is converted to a plain `let`, since the equality proof $e_=_$ and the elimination motive e_m are not needed at run time.

4.2.5 Quotient types

Figure 9 shows the rules for our quotient types, which follow the design of normalizable types [25]. The type erasure rules again turn the elimination into a plain let, and they also simply erase the two constructors, so we see that all the existential packages, all the quotienting and its normalization functions, and all the equality proofs disappear after type erasure as one would expect.

A type $\mathbb{Q} e_n$ is the type of values of type τ_1 quotiented by the normalization function e_n which returns the canonical representative of each equivalence class. $\mathbb{Q}\text{in}[e_n] e_v$ is the normal constructor and behaves a bit like a “smart” constructor in that it comes with a reduction rule which immediately normalizes it to $\mathbb{Q}n[e_n] (e_n e_v)$. If we consider only the typing and reduction rules, such quotients may seem useless: we could just replace $\mathbb{Q}\text{in}[e_n] e_v$ with $e_n e_v$ and do away with all the \mathbb{Q} and $\mathbb{Q}n$, and the code would still type-check. The benefit of our quotient types lies elsewhere: since the erasure of $\mathbb{Q}\text{in}[e_n] e_v$ is just $|e_v|$, the normalization does not take place at all during run time.

This distinction is crucial for us because our normalization functions return closure objects containing a non-closed function, so using them at run time would be simply impossible (or at least it would defeat the purpose of the closure conversion).

The rule $\mathbb{Q}\text{OUT}$ first checks that e_1 is well typed, which also returns the type $\mathbb{Q} e_n$ from which we can extract τ_1 which we need to type-check the body e_2 . Finally we check $e_=\mathbb{Q}$ which should guarantee that e_2 will not expose the differences between quotiented values that belong to the same equivalence class. We do that by requiring $e_=\mathbb{Q}$ to prove that e_2 returns the same answer whether or not normalization has been performed, which is the property we need to justify why normalization is performed during type checking but not during run time.

In return for this promise not to observe the differences hidden by the quotient, we get a stronger conversion rule thanks to the eager normalization performed by the reduction of $\mathbb{Q}\text{in}$.

4.2.6 Properties

Some of the basic metatheoretic properties of the target language are easy to establish:

LEMMA 3 (CONFLUENCE).

If $e \rightsquigarrow e_l$ and $e \rightsquigarrow e_r$, then there exists an e_m such that $e_l \rightsquigarrow e_m$ and $e_r \rightsquigarrow e_m$.

PROOF. By the usual Tait/Martin-Löf method. See Appendix A.1 for more details. \square

LEMMA 4 (TERM SUBSTITUTION).

Given $\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : \tau_2, \Gamma_2$ and $\Gamma_1 \vdash e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2$:

If $\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Rightarrow \tau_1$ then $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2[e_2/x] \vdash e_1[e_2/x] \Rightarrow \tau_1[e_2/x]$ and

If $\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Leftarrow \tau_1$ then $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2[e_2/x] \vdash e_1[e_2/x] \Leftarrow \tau_1[e_2/x]$.

PROOF. By induction on the typing derivation of e_1 . \square

LEMMA 5 (LEVEL SUBSTITUTION).

Given a well-formed context Γ :

If $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma[\ell/l] \vdash e[\ell/l] \Rightarrow \tau[\ell/l]$ and

If $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma[\ell/l] \vdash e[\ell/l] \Leftarrow \tau[\ell/l]$

PROOF. By induction on the typing derivation of e . \square

LEMMA 6 (STABILITY OF TYPING).

If $\vdash \Gamma'$ and $\Gamma \simeq \Gamma'$, then

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(evaluates) $v ::= \lambda x.e \mid \langle e_1, \dots, e_n \rangle$
 (eterms) $e ::= x \mid v \mid e_1 e_2 \mid e.i \mid \text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2$
 $\mid \mathcal{U} \mid \rightarrow \mid \langle \bullet \rangle \mid \exists \mid \text{Eq} \mid \mathbf{Q} \mid \text{refl}$
 (econtexts) $E ::= \bullet \mid E_1 e_2 \mid e_1 E_2 \mid \langle \vec{e}_b, E, \vec{e}_a \rangle \mid E.i \mid \text{let } x = E_1 \text{ in } e_2$

$e_1 \xrightarrow{e} e_2$ e_1 reduces to e_2 :

$$\begin{array}{l}
 (\lambda x.e_1) e_2 \xrightarrow{e} e_1[e_2/x] \qquad \langle e_1, \dots, e_n \rangle.i \xrightarrow{e} e_i \\
 \text{let } x = v \text{ in } e \xrightarrow{e} e[v/x] \qquad \frac{e \xrightarrow{e} e'}{E[e] \xrightarrow{e} E[e']}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 10. The type-erased language

- If $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$, and $\Gamma \vdash \tau' \Rightarrow s$, and $\tau \simeq \tau'$ then $\Gamma' \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau'$
- If $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'$.

PROOF. By induction on the typing derivation of e , see Appendix A.2. \square

Further in this paper we rely on this proof to allow ourselves to write $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau'$ when what we may really have is $\Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'$, since even though there may not be any typing derivation for $\Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau'$, the proof shows that we can always account for the discrepancy by inserting a RED at the point where we need such a derivation.

LEMMA 7 (SUBJECT REDUCTION).

Given $e \rightsquigarrow e'$, if $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma \vdash e' \Leftarrow \tau$,
and if $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma \vdash e' \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'$.

PROOF. By induction on $e \rightsquigarrow e'$ and the typing derivation of e . See further details in Appendix A.2. \square

LEMMA 8 (PROGRESS).

if $\bullet \vdash e : \tau$ either $e \rightsquigarrow e'$ or e is in weak head normal form.

PROOF. By induction on the typing derivation. See proof of a slightly different formulation in Appendix A.3. \square

Whether the target language is consistent and strongly normalizing is currently unknown. Almost all the constructs in the language are sufficiently well-understood that we can confidently say that they do not threaten consistency, with the single exception of the $\mathbf{U}\text{-}\exists$ rule whose soundness has not been seriously investigated. We discuss this in more detail in Section 6.5.

Type checking can be shown easily to be decidable, since all the rules are designed to represent an algorithm, with the notable exception of the RED rules which are not syntax directed. Of course, the proof can only succeed under the assumption that the language is strongly normalizing.

4.2.7 Type erasure

Fig. 10 shows the language used as the target of the erasure operation $|\cdot|$. The first line of the *eterms* shows this is simply an untyped lambda calculus with tuples and the rest are simply inert constants representing the type constructors of our target language. This time we explicitly define the evaluation contexts E and the associated congruence rule, because we want to exclude evaluation under binders.

The purpose of this language is to demonstrate that the erasure rules are sound in the sense that the elements we erase are not needed at run time:

LEMMA 9 (ERASURE SOUNDNESS).

If $\bullet \vdash e_1 : \tau$ and $|e_1| \xrightarrow{e} e_2$, then

there exists an e_3 such that $\bullet \vdash e_3 \Leftarrow \tau$ and $e_1 \simeq e_3$ and $|e_3| = e_2$.

PROOF. To reduce the set of cases to consider we start by reducing e_1 by any step that does not affect the erasure: $e_1 \rightsquigarrow e'_1 \wedge |e_1| = |e'_1|$. Assuming strong normalization, there can be only a finite number of such steps.

After that, the proof proceeds by induction on $\bullet \vdash e_1 \Leftarrow \tau$ and $|e_1| \xrightarrow{e} e_2$, using a lemma we call Weak head progress. This lemma states that a closed term either has a constructor as its head or can be reduced using a rule that reduces in an empty context and without using a normalization function, i.e. without reducing a Q_{in} to a Q_n .

When e_1 is of the form $\text{let}[e_=] Q_{in} x = Q_{in}[e_n] e_1$ in e_2 , before erasure e_1 reduces in two steps to $e_2[e_n e_1/x]$ whereas after erasure it reduces in one step to $|e_2|[[|e_1|/x]]$: The $e_=$ annotation gives us a proof that $e_2[e_n e_1/x]$ is propositionally equal to $e_2[e_1/x]$ and we use again the Weak head progress lemma, acting as a sort of canonical forms lemma, to show that $e_=$ has to be reducible to refl which means that the two expressions are not just propositionally but definitionally equal.

The detailed proof is in Appendix A.3. \square

5 Closure conversion

We can now show the actual closure conversion itself, denoted $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$, which is in Figure 11. We often use an abuse of notation where we write $\llbracket e \rrbracket$, but as you can see in that figure, the conversion algorithm does not take a mere term e as argument: it really operates on a typing derivation of e because it needs more type information than is readily provided in e itself. In contrast, $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ does return a mere term and not a full typing derivation. While we like to think of it as a conversion from intrinsically typed terms to intrinsically typed terms, we prefer to return a mere term so that we can separately state and prove that it does indeed preserve typing.

We use the following auxiliary definitions:

- **clotype** $\tau_1 x.\tau_2$: The *non-quotiented* type of a closure that takes an argument of type τ_1 to a result of type τ_2 , where τ_2 can refer to the argument under the name x . This is the type of a 4-tuple made of (in reverse order) a closed function we denote as *code*, a captured environment *env*, its type t , and its universe level l .
- **call** $c x$: The code of a call to the non-quotiented closure c with argument x . This proceeds by unpacking the 4-tuple to then invoke the *code* with a triplet of the *env*, the actual argument, and the trivial refl proof that the first argument is indeed *env*.

$$\begin{aligned}
1072 \quad \text{clotype } \tau_1 x. \tau_2 &= \exists l. \exists t. \mathcal{U}_l. \langle \text{env} : t, \text{code} : \langle x_e : t, x : \tau_1, p : (x_e = \text{env}) \rangle \rangle \rightarrow \tau_2 \\
1073 \quad \text{call} &: (\text{clotype } \tau_1 x. \tau_2) \rightarrow (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \\
1074 \quad \text{call } c \ x &= \text{let } \langle l; \langle t; \langle \text{env}, \text{code} \rangle \rangle \rangle = c \text{ in } \text{code } \langle \text{env}, x, \text{refl} \rangle \\
1075 \quad \text{norm } clo &= (\lambda c. \langle l; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. \text{call } c \ x \rangle \rangle \rangle : clo \rightarrow clo) \\
1076 \quad \text{tfv}(\Gamma, e) &= \bigcup_{x \in \text{fv}(e)} \{x\} \cup \text{tfv}(\Gamma, \Gamma(x)) \\
1077 & \\
1078 & \\
1079 \quad \left[\frac{\tau_1 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_2 \quad \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_1} (\text{RED}_C) \right] &= \llbracket \Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket \\
1080 & \\
1081 \quad \left[\frac{\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_1 \quad \tau_1 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_2} (\text{RED}_S) \right] &= \llbracket \Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau_1 \rrbracket \\
1082 & \\
1083 \quad \left[\frac{\Gamma \vdash N \Rightarrow \tau_1 \quad \tau_1 \simeq \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash [N] \Leftarrow \tau_2} (\text{CONV}) \right] &= \llbracket \Gamma \vdash N \Rightarrow \tau_1 \rrbracket \\
1084 & \\
1085 \quad \left[\frac{\Gamma(x) = \tau}{\Gamma \vdash x \Rightarrow \tau} (\text{VAR}) \right] &= x \\
1086 & \\
1087 \quad \left[\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{U}_\ell \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{(S \ell)} (\text{SORT}) \right] &= \mathcal{U}_\ell \quad \text{because we chose } \llbracket \ell \rrbracket = \ell \\
1088 & \\
1089 \quad \left[\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s \quad \Gamma \vdash M \Leftarrow \tau}{\Gamma \vdash (M : \tau) \Rightarrow \tau} (\text{ANN}) \right] &= (\llbracket \Gamma \vdash M \Leftarrow \tau \rrbracket : \llbracket \Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s \rrbracket) \\
1090 & \\
1091 \quad \left[\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1} \quad \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2} \quad \ell_3 = \max(\ell_1, \ell_2)}{\Gamma \vdash (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_3}} (\text{PI}) \right] & \\
1092 & \\
1093 \quad = \text{Q}(\text{norm}(\text{clotype } \llbracket \Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1} \rrbracket x. \llbracket \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2} \rrbracket)) & \\
1094 & \\
1095 \quad \left[\frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Rightarrow (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2 \Leftarrow \tau_1}{\Gamma \vdash e_1 e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2[(e_2 : \tau_1)/x]} (\text{APP}) \right] & \\
1096 & \\
1097 \quad = \text{let}[\text{refl}] \text{Qin } c = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash e_1 \Rightarrow (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket \text{ in } \text{call } c \ \llbracket \Gamma \vdash e_2 \Leftarrow \tau_1 \rrbracket & \\
1098 & \\
1099 \quad \left[\frac{\Gamma, x_a : \tau_a \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_r}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x_a. e \Leftarrow ((x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r)} (\text{LAM}) \right] & \\
1100 & \\
1101 \quad = \text{Qin}[(\text{norm } clo)] & \\
1102 & \\
1103 \quad \langle \ell; \langle \langle \llbracket \Gamma' \rrbracket \rangle; \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_- \rangle. \text{body} \rangle \rangle \rangle : clo & \\
1104 & \\
1105 \quad \text{where } \tau'_a &= \llbracket \Gamma \vdash \tau_a \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_a} \rrbracket \\
1106 \quad \tau'_r &= \llbracket \Gamma, x_a : \tau_a \vdash \tau_r \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_r} \rrbracket \\
1107 \quad clo &= \text{clotype } \tau'_a x_a. \tau'_r \\
1108 \quad \vec{x}_f &= \text{tfv}(\Gamma, \lambda x_a. e) \cup \text{tfv}(\Gamma, (x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r) \quad \text{Find the free variables} \\
1109 & \\
1110 \quad \Gamma' &= \Gamma |_{\vec{x}_f} = \vec{x} : \vec{\tau} \quad \text{Get their type and order them} \\
1111 \quad \Gamma \vdash \langle \Gamma' \rangle &\Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_\ell \quad \text{Compute the universe level } \ell \\
1112 \quad f_m &= \lambda \langle \vec{x} \rangle. (x_a : \tau'_a) \rightarrow \tau'_r \quad \text{The motive of the cast} \\
1113 \quad \text{body} &= \text{letcast}[f_m, x_-] x_a = x'_a \text{ in} \\
1114 \quad \text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = x_e &\text{ in } \llbracket \Gamma, x_a : \tau_a \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_r \rrbracket \\
1115 & \\
1116 & \\
1117 & \\
1118 & \\
1119 & \\
1120 & \\
1121 & \\
1122 &
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 11. The closure conversion itself

- 1123 • `norm clo`: The normalization function for closures of type `clo`. This returns the
- 1124 function fully annotated with its type since it will be used in places where we need to
- 1125 be able to synthesize the type.
- 1126 • `tfv(Γ, e)`: The set of transitively free variables, which includes the free variables of
- 1127 the types of the free variables.
- 1128

1129 The first few cases of the closure conversion just recurse through the derivation. The first
 1130 interesting case is the one for $(x: \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2$ where we state that the type of a closure is a
 1131 quotient of the 4-tuple defined by `clotype`.

1132 The case for $e_1 e_2$ takes such a closure object and calls it: it first looks inside the quotiented
 1133 object and then uses `call` to perform the actual function invocation. The proof that this obeys
 1134 the quotient's equality is provided by another `refl` because `call (norm ... c) e` simply reduces
 1135 to `call c e`: all the constructors introduced by `norm` find their corresponding elimination forms
 1136 in `call`.

1137 The hard work is all concentrated in the case for $\lambda x_a. e$: there we actually build the closure
 1138 object, made of its quotiented existential nested tuples, as well as the closed code:

- 1139 • We start by computing τ'_a and τ'_r which are the converted types corresponding the
- 1140 τ_a and τ_r . This requires extracting the sub-derivations of τ_a and τ_r from the typing
- 1141 derivation of $(x_a: \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r$.
- 1142 • x_e is the formal variable that will hold the tuple of captured variables.
- 1143 • x_a is the function's formal argument. In the source code its type is defined in the
- 1144 ambient context Γ of the function, obviously. But in the converted code, this is not
- 1145 so simple because from the outside of the closure we also want the type to refer to
- 1146 elements of the ambient context Γ , but the body of the code cannot and has to refer
- 1147 to those same elements via the argument x_e instead, which will contain the captured
- 1148 environment. For this reason, in the converted code, the source x_a ends up split into
- 1149 x'_a with the “outside” type and x_a with the “inside” type.
- 1150 • \vec{x}_f is the set of captured variables, in no particular order. We compute it using `tfv`
- 1151 which gives us the set of transitively free variables.
- 1152 • \vec{x} is this same set but properly ordered according to the order in which they appear in
- 1153 the environment, so that dependencies between them are obeyed.
- 1154 • $\langle \llbracket \Gamma' \rrbracket \rangle$, also known as $\langle \vec{x} : \llbracket \vec{\tau} \rrbracket \rangle$, is the type of the `env` tuple holding the captured
- 1155 variables. Here again, $\llbracket \vec{\tau}_i \rrbracket$ really means to apply the closure conversion to the
- 1156 derivation of the type of x_i found within the typing derivation of Γ .
- 1157 • ℓ is the universe level of $\langle \llbracket \Gamma' \rrbracket \rangle$.
- 1158 • The closed function then just takes its three arguments x_e, x'_a , and $x_=_$ (seen on the
- 1159 2nd line of the code), after which `body` unpacks the environment x_e with a `let` which
- 1160 (re)introduces all the free variables expected by the original body of the function and
- 1161 then evaluates the closure converted body $\llbracket \Gamma, x_a: \tau_a \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_r \rrbracket$, while carefully
- 1162 using $x_=_$ to mediate between the “inside” types and the “outside” types.
- 1163
- 1164
- 1165
- 1166
- 1167
- 1168
- 1169
- 1170
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- 1172
- 1173

5.1 Properties

1170 Our closure conversion algorithm is designed like a syntactic model, following the approach
 1171 advocated by Boulier et al. [6].

1174 LEMMA 10 (SUBSTITUTION COMMUTES).

1175 Given $\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : \tau_x, \Gamma_2$ and $\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1$ and $\Gamma_1 \vdash e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_x$, let $e'_2 = \llbracket \Gamma_1 \vdash e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_x \rrbracket$:
 1176 then for all $e_s = \llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2[e_2/x] \vdash e_1[e_2/x] : \tau_1[e_2/x] \rrbracket$
 1177 there exists an $e_c = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rrbracket$ such that $e_s \simeq e_c[e'_2/x]$.
 1178

1179 PROOF. The $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ notation is a bit misleading because it gives the false impression that the
 1180 closure conversion is a function of Γ , e , and τ , but this is not quite true because for any
 1181 such triplet there can be several different typing derivations which internally assign slightly
 1182 different types to the same subterms, and indeed the closure conversion can return different
 1183 results for those derivations because in the closure conversion of LAM, parts of the type of
 1184 the λ -expression appear (closure-converted) in the result of the closure conversion.
 1185

1186 For this reason we need the universal and existential quantifiers above to clarify exactly
 1187 what we mean.

1188 The proof proceeds by induction on the typing derivation of e_1 . When e_1 is not a lambda
 1189 expression, the induction proceeds by extracting from e_s the subterms of the nested calls to
 1190 $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ and use the i.h. on them, after which we can conclude by rebuilding an e_c that is shown
 1191 to be equal using the definition of the substitution and the congruence of definitional equality.
 1192 For the lambda case, the closure conversion of the lambda before and after substitution leads
 1193 to quite different results since the set of free variables is changed. The proof hinges on the use
 1194 of the QIN normalization of the quotient type. It starts by using the induction hypothesis to
 1195 show that both conversions will return quotients of the same type and hence using the same
 1196 normalization function, and then applies on both sides the shared normalization function,
 1197 which ends up undoing the closure conversion.
 1198

1199 Further details can be found in Appendix A.4. □

1200

1201 THEOREM 1 (COMPUTATIONAL SOUNDNESS).

1202 If $\Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1$ and $\Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2$ and $\Gamma_1 \simeq \Gamma_2$ and $e_1 \simeq e_2$ and $\tau_1 \simeq \tau_2$,
 1203 then $\llbracket \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rrbracket \simeq \llbracket \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2 \rrbracket$.

1204

1205 PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $e_1 \simeq e_2$ and that of the typing of e_1 . The
 1206 non-trivial case is the β -reduction rule, where we see again that the various introduction forms
 1207 used by the encoding of the λ -expression are all canceled by the corresponding elimination
 1208 forms of the encoding of the application.

1209 The detailed proof is in Appendix A.5. □

1210

1211 The computational soundness lemma justifies the abuse of notation of $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$: while the exact
 1212 code it returns depends on the exact typing derivation passed to it, they are all definitionally
 1213 equivalent.
 1214

1215 THEOREM 2 (TYPING SOUNDNESS).

1216 If $\Gamma \vdash e : \tau$, let $\Gamma' = \llbracket \vdash \Gamma \rrbracket$, $e' = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash e : \tau \rrbracket$, and $\tau' = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash \tau \Rightarrow s \rrbracket$ then $\Gamma' \vdash e' \Leftarrow \tau'$.

1217

1218 PROOF. The proof is by induction on the typing derivation. It follows the same general
 1219 structure as the usual proof of type preservation of closure conversion, such as found in [30].

1220 The detailed proof is in Appendix A.6. □

1221

1222 LEMMA 11 (CLOSEDNESS).

1223 If $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$, for all λ -expressions $\lambda x.e'$ in $\llbracket \Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau \rrbracket$ we have that $fv(\lambda x.e') = \emptyset$.

1224

1225 **PROOF.** By induction on the typing derivation. Most of the $\lambda x.e$ that can occur in the
 1226 converted code appear in type annotations and get stripped away by the type erasure, such as
 1227 the norm used in the quotient type of functions. The only $\lambda x.e$ that still appear after erasure
 1228 are the main ones, which get stashed on the *code* slot of the closure, and these are indeed
 1229 closed thanks to the *let* and *letcast* placed around the body to rebind its free variables. \square
 1230

1231 5.2 Closure converting a bigger language

1233 Our source language was purposefully very limited, so that we could focus on the important
 1234 elements, but of course we want to be able to scale this to a more realistic language. Luckily,
 1235 this source language also hits the most problematic spots of closure conversion, so it is
 1236 straightforward to extend our result to a more general source language.

1237 To get started, we can extend our source language with (dependent) tuples, using the same
 1238 syntax and rules as we used in our target language. Extending the conversion function to
 1239 handle these constructs is simply:
 1240

$$\begin{aligned}
 1241 \llbracket \langle \Gamma \rangle \rrbracket &= \langle \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \rangle \\
 1242 \llbracket \langle \vec{e} \rangle \rrbracket &= \langle \llbracket \vec{e} \rrbracket \rangle \\
 1243 \llbracket e.i \rrbracket &= \llbracket e \rrbracket.i
 \end{aligned}$$

1244 Adding support for existential types is similarly simple:
 1245

$$\begin{aligned}
 1246 \llbracket \exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2 \rrbracket &= \exists x : \llbracket \tau_1 \rrbracket. \llbracket \tau_2 \rrbracket \\
 1247 \llbracket \langle e_1 ; e_2 \rangle \rrbracket &= \langle \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket ; \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \rangle \\
 1248 \llbracket \text{let } \langle x_1 ; x_2 \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rrbracket &= \text{let } \langle x_1 ; x_2 \rangle = \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \text{ in } \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket
 \end{aligned}$$

1253 5.3 Closing the loop

1254 The main motivation for this work is to replace the custom constructs used until now for
 1255 closure conversion with more generic ones. Of course, by their generic nature, it is desirable
 1256 to support them also in the source language. And indeed we can!

1257 We can easily extend our source language with the same \exists quantification over universe
 1258 levels as we have in our target language. Universe levels are second class citizens which can
 1259 be erased, just like types in System F, so our closures do not need to close over universe level
 1260 variables, which means we can use the same simple approach as was used in [28]:
 1261

$$\begin{aligned}
 1262 \llbracket \exists l. \tau \rrbracket &= \exists l. \llbracket \tau \rrbracket \\
 1263 \llbracket \langle \ell ; e \rangle \rrbracket &= \langle \ell ; \llbracket e \rrbracket \rangle \\
 1264 \llbracket \text{let } \langle l ; x \rangle = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rrbracket &= \text{let } \langle l ; x \rangle = \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \text{ in } \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket
 \end{aligned}$$

1265 In order for this to work correctly, one has to be careful to define $\text{fv}(e)$ such that it only
 1266 considers term variables x and ignores universe level variables l . This can be just as easily
 1267 extended with \forall quantification over universe levels.

1268 Finally, we can extend our source language to be the same as our target language by adding
 1269 the remaining equality and quotient types. But this hits a minor hurdle: some of the new
 1270 constructs such as *letcast* or \mathbb{Q} take arguments which are expected to be functions so when
 1271 closure converting them we have to be careful not to convert those functions into closures.
 1272
 1273
 1274
 1275

1276 There are various ways to circumvent the problem, but the simplest is to η -expand them:

$$\begin{aligned}
1277 & \\
1278 & \llbracket \text{Eq } e_1 e_2 \rrbracket &= \text{Eq } \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \\
1279 & \llbracket \text{refl} \rrbracket &= \text{refl} \\
1280 & \llbracket \text{letcast}[e_m, e_=] x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rrbracket &= \text{letcast}[\lambda y. \llbracket e_m y \rrbracket, \llbracket e_= \rrbracket] x = \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \text{ in } \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \\
1281 & \llbracket \text{Q } e_n \rrbracket &= \text{Q } (\lambda x. \llbracket e_n x \rrbracket) \\
1282 & \llbracket \text{Qin}[e_n] e_v \rrbracket &= \text{Qin}[\lambda x. \llbracket e_n x \rrbracket] \llbracket e_v \rrbracket \\
1283 & \llbracket \text{let}[e_=] \text{Qin } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \rrbracket &= \\
1284 & & \text{let}[\lambda x_1. \lambda x_2. \lambda x_=. \llbracket e_= x_1 x_2 x_= \rrbracket] \text{Qin } x = \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \text{ in } \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \\
1285 & & \\
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1322 & & \\
1323 & & \\
1324 & & \\
1325 & & \\
1326 & &
\end{aligned}$$

1286 As you can see, it's not a plain η -expansion: the new lambdas are outside of the $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$, which
1287 means they will not be closure-converted. For example in the case of $\llbracket \text{Q } e_n \rrbracket$, e_n may itself
1288 be a λ -expression and that one *will* be converted to a closure, but $\lambda x. \llbracket e_n x \rrbracket$ wraps it into the
1289 form of a normal (not necessarily closed) function, like those expected by Q.
1290

1291 Note that this works only because those places where we need to keep using actual functions
1292 are all erased anyway, so it does not matter if the λ -expressions we generate for them are not
1293 closed. For constructs that take function arguments and whose arguments are *not* erased, we
1294 would need to find other solutions, like what we did when we turned `cast` into `letcast`.
1295

1296 With these extensions, our closure conversion algorithm should accept the same input
1297 language as its output language. Ideally, we would like our target language to enjoy the
1298 property that all the non-erasable functions are closed, i.e. that Lemma 11 is not a property
1299 of our closure conversion algorithm but a property of the target language, thereby expressing
1300 the fact that this language is computationally simpler than the source language, as is desirable
1301 in a compilation stage. There is no fundamental difficulty in doing so, but we felt that such
1302 additional annotations would distract from the core contributions.
1303

1304 6 Discussion

1305 Our aim was to cover a fairly realistic source language and to use a target language that is
1306 as generic as we can. Here we discuss several design decisions as well as the limits of our
1307 current work.
1308

1309 6.1 Related work

1310 6.1.1 Type-preserving conversion with dependent types

1311 There are very few attempts to implement a type preserving closure conversion of a dependently
1312 typed language in the literature.
1313

1314 The first we could find is by Shao et al. [32], where they show a different way to do it: the
1315 source language is divided into two layers, where the bottom one is not dependently typed,
1316 allowing them to perform closure conversion without touching the dependent types.
1317

1318 Monnier and Haguenaer [27] do not actually present a closure conversion, but instead
1319 present a conversion from a dependently typed language to a language where the dependencies
1320 are encoded as singleton types, after which they argue that a more or less standard closure
1321 conversion can be used. It is not clear if that would really handle a tower of universes.
1322

1323 Bowman and Ahmed [8] show not only the closure conversion algorithm for a calculus
1324 with dependent types but also prove that the target language is consistent. While their source
1325 language does not include a tower of universes, it might be possible to make their approach
1326

1327 handle such a tower. As discussed earlier, they rely on language constructs custom-designed
1328 to represent closures.

1329 Bowman [7] shows an alternative approach that relies on an impredicative existential
1330 quantification instead of a custom language construct, but still has to resort to a custom η
1331 equivalence rule for those existential packages representing closures, in order to preserve
1332 equality of closure-converted functions. They rely on Prop-style impredicativity which limits
1333 that work to a single universe.

1334 In the vicinity, Bowman et al. [9] shows how to perform a CPS conversion for a dependently
1335 typed language. Like the previous work, it does not rely on custom constructs but it relies on
1336 a Prop-style impredicativity which limits it to a single universe.

1337
1338 More recently Koronkevich et al. [22] attacked the related problem of a conversion to
1339 A-normal form for a dependently typed language. As expected, this proves an easier target
1340 and they manage to handle a language with the full universe tower and without requiring any
1341 form of impredicativity.

1342 Sullivan et al. [33] do not tackle dependent types, but they attack related questions such
1343 as how to preserve the semantics of function equality across code transformation, focusing
1344 on closure conversion. In their system, they even manage to preserve equality between the
1345 function before and after closure conversion, a bit like our quotients' normalization function
1346 is able to turn a closure-converted function back into an unclosed form.

1348 6.1.2 Universe polymorphism

1349 Hou (Favonia) et al. [19] present a language with explicit universe polymorphism, but
1350 restricted to prenex forms, which are not sufficient for our needs.

1351
1352 Bezem et al. [5] show a λ -calculus with a form of universe polymorphism similar to the
1353 one we use in Section 4.2.3, where universe levels are also second class citizens but are not
1354 restricted to prenex form. Their system extends ours with product types indexed not just with
1355 universe levels but also with universe constraints. But their universe-indexed types do not
1356 themselves have types and their language is fully predicative. We can view our $U-\exists$ rule as a
1357 way to solve both of those restrictions.

1358
1359 Another λ -calculus with explicit universe polymorphism is proposed by Kovács [23] who
1360 manages to make universe levels first class. More recently, Chan and Weirich [10] proposed a
1361 calculus which also offers first class universe levels and constraints. As with the previous
1362 works, these are limited to a predicative language, and an impredicative rule like $U-\exists$ would
1363 likely make them inconsistent.

1365 6.1.3 Encoding standard language constructs

1366
1367 Like CPS and closure conversions which try to encode standard functions into a lower-level
1368 language without an activation stack or without closures, the following articles try to encode
1369 inductive types into a language without those constructs.

1370 Firsov and Stump [15] show how to make a Church-style impredicative encoding of
1371 induction types which allows not just recursion but induction. They use a “pure” typed
1372 λ -calculus in a Curry-style presentation, where they rely on a dependent conjunction type to
1373 circumvent the usual impossibility of induction for such encodings.

1374
1375 Awodey et al. [1] solve this same problem taking ideas from homotopy type theory instead,
1376 and extending it to some higher inductive types.

1377

Jenkins et al. [21] attack the other weakness of impredicative encodings of inductive types: the inability to eliminate those encodings to higher universes. They present a way to encode strong eliminations in a calculus with only one universe.

6.2 Source language features

While our source language does not cover all of the features of a real language like Idris or Agda, we do cover a significant part. The main missing functionality would be things like inductive types, coinductive types, a Prop universe, erasable arguments, and linearity.

Based on past experience with type-preserving closure conversion in non-dependent settings, we do not expect any significant difficulty adding support for inductive types: we already support dependent tuples and equality types, so fundamentally all that is missing is sum types and recursive types, neither of which usually interacts in any way with closure conversion, where the type preservation proof proceeds directly by applying the induction hypothesis. We can of course expect some superficial obstacles like those that forced us to replace `cast` with `letcast`, and clearly there could be additional complications linked to the usual syntactic termination checks which will likely tend to get confused by the layers of tuples and `letcast` added by the closure conversion. At the same time, the range of difficulties introduced by dependent types during closure conversion cannot be overstated, so it is of course possible that some nasty surprises may be lurking there, despite our optimistic expectations. The same should hold for coinductive types.

In contrast, it is very much unclear how an impredicative Prop universe would interact with the rest of this language. Maybe the fact that terms from the Prop universe can be erased could save us from having to figure it out. It is also unclear how the impredicativity already provided by our language compares to that of Prop.

Adding support for erasable arguments and linearity seems to fall in-between. It is not immediately obvious, but it might be feasible: adding those features to the language itself should not pose any specific difficulty; the main difficulty would be performing closure conversion without changing the erasability/linearity of variables.

6.3 Efficiency

Performing closure conversion correctly is a good first step, but generating efficient code is also important. The current closure conversion is not satisfactory in this regard and solving some of those issues may not be straightforward.

- The main issue with our conversion is that after type erasure, our closures are represented as pairs of the captured environment and the code. While this is the “official” definition of a closure, in practice closures are more often implemented by merging the inner tuple representing the environment with the outer pair, resulting in a single tuple that contains the code in one field and the free variables in the other fields. Furthermore, the code receives as argument not just the environment, but the whole closure (since they do not exist separately any more), requiring a non-trivial form of self-application. Geller et al. [16] investigates those problems and proposes solutions, but it is not immediately clear how those solutions can be adapted to the current work,
- A more subtle aspect is that it is common to place the code in the first field and the captured variables afterwards, whereas our encoding requires fundamentally

the environment to come first because the type of the code must refer to the environment. Dependent type systems always assume a kind of left-to-right ordering of dependencies, but sometimes practical concerns may require fields to be laid out differently. At the lower level these ordering issues should not matter, and in a sense, this is a merely cosmetic issue, but it would be good to encode dependencies separately from the ordering,

- Compilation time could also prove to be an issue: our representation of closures before type erasure is fairly verbose with many layers of wrapping which are meant to be erased but still cost resources during compilation up until the time we can perform the erasure. Whether this would prove significant in a real compiler is unclear at this stage, as are the mitigating measures one could take if needed.
- Another serious limitation of our conversion is that our closures capture the whole set of *transitively* free variables, even though at run time only the truly free variables are required. It should be possible to solve this problem by marking some of the fields in the tuples as erasable, but we have not investigated this yet.

On the other hand, it should be possible to adapt our conversion algorithm to other non-flat closure representations such as that of Shao [31] without changing our target language. This kind of flexibility is one of the benefits of representing closure objects as normal tuples rather than custom constructs.

6.4 Quotient types

Our approach is not necessarily tied to the specific choice of quotient type we decided to use, but the more common presentations of higher inductive types and quotient types do not offer a strengthened definitional equality, making it necessary to manipulate propositional proofs of equality between closures. This in turn would require the same kind of efforts as required to convert code from ETT to ITT [38]. We see no reason to think it cannot be made to work, but we have not tried to work out the details.

Similarly, we have not really tried to make our approach work with other quotient types like those of Cohen [12] or Courtieu [13] which are also based on normalization functions but they do not seem to be directly usable because they presume that the normalization function will also be used at run time, which we cannot afford.

6.5 Impredicative Universe Quantification

The majority of the features we add to our target language to support closure conversion can be argued to be not only generic, in the sense that they can have many other uses, but also fairly standard in the sense that they, or variants of them, are already studied in several other languages. There is one major exception: the rule we use to type our existential universe types.

While languages like Agda support universe polymorphism as well as existential quantification over universe levels, they do it in a predicative way, typically placing such a quantified type as $\exists l. \tau$ into a universe over which they cannot quantify, such as \mathcal{U}_ω , regardless of τ . As discussed above, there is a fair bit of recent research around universe polymorphism [5, 10, 19, 23], but they stay within a clearly predicative world or at most accommodate a single Prop-style impredicative universe, whereas closure conversion cannot preserve types without *some form* of impredicativity in all universes.

1480 In contrast to Agda, we place such a type into the universe $\mathcal{U}_{\ell[0/l]}$, making it impredicative.
 1481 As explained in Section 3.2, this rule is the one that our closure conversion *suggested*.

1482 While this novel rule is unsatisfactory given our quest for “generic language constructs”,
 1483 it should be noted that the language construct in itself is still generic in two ways: first,
 1484 it uses similar syntax and dynamic semantics as in Agda and papers presenting universe
 1485 polymorphism, so the novelty is limited to the details of the typing rule for universe
 1486 quantification, and this should have a more limited impact on compilers. More importantly,
 1487 rather than being specific to closure conversion, such a functionality would be generally
 1488 useful as a new form of impredicativity, potentially replacing the usual Prop universe in this
 1489 role.
 1490

1491 6.5.1 Threats to consistency

1492
 1493 While our minimal source language is known to be sound, the logical consistency of our target
 1494 language is a big question mark because of its reliance on this novel notion of impredicativity
 1495 introduced by more aggressive rules for universe polymorphism.

1496 Impredicativity is a well known source of inconsistency, which is even the original
 1497 motivation for the invention of types by Bertrand Russell. So requiring a new form of
 1498 impredicativity is potentially problematic. We have not yet been able to prove the relative
 1499 consistency of this kind of impredicativity. Proofs of consistency of languages with universe
 1500 levels define their model by induction over the naturals representing the universe levels. For
 1501 example Chan and Weirich [10] define their model as a function parameterized by a bound i on
 1502 the largest universe and then by induction on the naturals show that it is valid for all universe
 1503 levels. The typing rule we use for quantification over levels breaks the well-foundedness used
 1504 to justify that induction.
 1505

1506 As mentioned in Section 4.2.3, this is a qualitatively different kind of impredicativity than
 1507 the traditional one seen in Prop. In our calculus, the bottom universe 0 is no less predicative
 1508 than the others.³ More importantly, this is not about specific universes being impredicative or
 1509 not. To some extent it can be compared to known forms of impredicativity, as was shown by
 1510 Monnier and Bos [26] who prove that a similar impredicative universe quantification rule,
 1511 applied to \forall rather than \exists , is able to encode System F.
 1512

1513 6.5.2 Alternatives

1514
 1515 We do not know that our calculus is consistent but we can’t see how to type closure converted
 1516 code of a source language with a tower of universes without using something similar to the
 1517 rules we propose: in a sense, the rules we use arise naturally in our encoding. Of course, there
 1518 is always the emergency escape hatch of resorting to custom-made constructs like the one
 1519 used in [8].

1520 Our hope is that even if it proves unsound, there might still be a more restrictive version
 1521 of it which is sound and which at the same time covers the very specific use we make of it.
 1522 For example, our encoding could make do with a simpler construct $\exists t. \tau$ which would be
 1523 equivalent to $\exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \tau$ but without giving access to l .
 1524

1525 While the rule we use may ultimately prove dangerous in general, we do believe it to give
 1526 the correct result for the specific case where the existential type is the form we use because
 1527

1528 ³Actually, one could argue that our \mathcal{U}_0 is “more predicative” since, as we noted in that same section, $\exists l. \tau$ can
 1529 belong to universe 0 only in trivial cases.
 1530

1531 those existential types are equivalent to the closures they represent from our source language,
 1532 which is known to be consistent and does not involve any impredicativity: since the l of an
 1533 object of type $\exists l.\tau$ is erasable, we cannot extract l out of it, nor can we extract from it any
 1534 type that belongs to \mathcal{U}_l (such as the t of the inner existential), nor for that matter any value
 1535 whose type belongs to \mathcal{U}_l (such as the field *env*) or contains an element that belongs to \mathcal{U}_l
 1536 (such as the field *code*), so really, the only thing we can do with those closure objects is to
 1537 call them.
 1538

1540 6.5.3 Signs of consistency

1541 In the specific way the \exists quantification is used here, the rules proposed seem eminently
 1542 reasonable: they place the closure objects right in the exact same universe level that their
 1543 original λ -expression occupied in the source code. Sadly, that does not guarantee that they
 1544 are sound in general.
 1545

1546 This said, we have attempted to encode known paradoxes such as that of Hurkens [20]
 1547 in our target language system, and so far those attempts have not borne fruits. To give an
 1548 example, some of those paradoxes begin by defining something like an ordering, represented
 1549 by a type of the form $\langle t:\mathcal{U}_\ell, < : t \rightarrow t \rightarrow \mathcal{U}, \dots \rangle$ and then want to define the ordering of all
 1550 orderings, which requires some form of impredicativity. To make use of our impredicativity
 1551 the natural choice is to use a type like $\exists l.\langle t:\mathcal{U}_l, < : t \rightarrow t \rightarrow \mathcal{U}, \dots \rangle$, but then we aren't
 1552 able to define an ordering between elements of this type because we cannot extract much
 1553 useful information out of it, for the same reasons as mentioned above: since universe levels
 1554 are second class we cannot project them out of the existential, which then prevents us from
 1555 projecting the field t because its type would require projecting l , and this in turn also prevents
 1556 us from projecting anything that mentions l or t out of this structure. So while it is not known
 1557 to be consistent, it is currently not known to be inconsistent either. Of course it might be just
 1558 a reflection of our inexperience.
 1559

1560 One possible intuition as for why impredicative universe quantification *may* not be
 1561 completely crazy is that the second-class status of universe levels makes universe polymorphic
 1562 definitions enjoy a strong form of parametricity, which seems to be an important requirement
 1563 for impredicativity to remain sound [18]. Agda's position says that $\forall l.\tau$ can be modeled as a
 1564 set theoretic function which for every level l returns the corresponding τ , so this function is
 1565 clearly very large since it includes all the possible τ one can get for all the possible levels
 1566 with which we can instantiate it. For this reason, if $\Gamma \vdash \tau : \mathcal{U}_\ell$, Agda places $\forall l.\tau$ in the
 1567 universe $\sup_l \ell$ which they represent as ω . Our typing rules basically take the opposite
 1568 position, considering that the type $\forall l.\tau$ is arguably smaller than any given instantiation of τ
 1569 since it only holds those rare functions which can be used at any universe level (just like the
 1570 type $\forall t.t \rightarrow t$ is so small that it only contains a single element), so it places it in the universe
 1571 $\inf_l \ell$, hence $\ell[0/l]$.
 1572
 1573
 1574

1575 7 Conclusion

1576 We have shown a target language together with a closure conversion algorithm that is able to
 1577 handle a source language with dependent types, a tower of universes, and all that without
 1578 resorting to the use of custom-made constructs. We also sketched how to extend it with tuples
 1579 and all the other features supported by the target language, including universe polymorphism.
 1580
 1581

The main ingredients to get that novel result are quotient types and impredicative universe polymorphism, the latter of which is an as-yet poorly understood feature that will require further study to find out if it is consistent, and if not, whether some weaker form can be found that preserves consistency while still allowing uses such as closure conversion.

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Reduction Rules:

$$\frac{e \Rightarrow e'}{[(e : \tau)] \Rightarrow e'} \quad \frac{e_1 \Rightarrow e'_1 \quad e_2 \Rightarrow e'_2 \quad \tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau'_1 \quad \tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau'_2}{((\lambda x.e_1) : (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \Rightarrow (e'_1 : \tau'_2)[(e'_2 : \tau'_1)/x]} \quad (\beta) \quad \dots$$

$$\frac{\ell \Rightarrow \ell'}{0 \sqcup \ell \Rightarrow \ell'} \quad \frac{\ell \Rightarrow \ell'}{\ell \sqcup 0 \Rightarrow \ell'} \quad \frac{\ell_1 \Rightarrow \ell'_1 \quad \ell_2 \Rightarrow \ell'_2}{S \ell_1 \sqcup S \ell_2 \Rightarrow S (\ell'_1 \sqcup \ell'_2)} \quad \dots$$

$$\frac{e_n \Rightarrow e'_n \quad e \Rightarrow e'}{\text{Qin}[e_n] e \Rightarrow \text{Qn}[e'_n] (e'_n e')} \quad \frac{e_v \Rightarrow e'_v \quad e_ = \Rightarrow e'_ = \quad e_n \Rightarrow e'_n \quad e_b \Rightarrow e'_b}{\text{let}[e_ =] \text{Qin } x = \text{Qn}[e_n] e_v \text{ in } e_b \rightsquigarrow e'_b[e'_v/x]}$$

Structural rules:

$$e \Rightarrow e \quad \frac{e_1 \Rightarrow e'_1 \quad e_2 \Rightarrow e'_2}{e_1 e_2 \Rightarrow e'_1 e'_2} \quad \frac{e \Rightarrow e' \quad \tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau'_1}{(e : \tau_1) \Rightarrow (e' : \tau'_1)} \quad \frac{e \Rightarrow e'}{\lambda x.e \Rightarrow \lambda x.e'}$$

$$\dots \quad \frac{\ell \Rightarrow \ell'}{S \ell \Rightarrow S \ell'} \quad \frac{\ell_1 \Rightarrow \ell'_1 \quad \ell_2 \Rightarrow \ell'_2}{\ell_1 \sqcup \ell_2 \Rightarrow \ell'_1 \sqcup \ell'_2} \quad \dots$$

$$\frac{e \Rightarrow e' \quad e_ = \Rightarrow e'_ = \quad e_b \Rightarrow e'_b}{\text{let}[e_ =] \text{Qin } x = e \text{ in } e_b \rightsquigarrow \text{let}[e'_ =] \text{Qin } x = e' \text{ in } e'_b} \quad \frac{e_n \Rightarrow e'_n}{\text{Q } e_n \Rightarrow \text{Q } e'_n}$$

$$\frac{e_n \Rightarrow e'_n \quad e \Rightarrow e'}{\text{Qn}[e_n] e \Rightarrow \text{Qn}[e'_n] e'} \quad \frac{e_n \Rightarrow e'_n \quad e \Rightarrow e'}{\text{Qin}[e_n] e \Rightarrow \text{Qin}[e'_n] e'}$$

Fig. 12. Excerpts from the definition of parallel reduction \Rightarrow .

A Proofs

A.1 Proof of Lemma 3: Confluence

This proof follows the usual parallel reduction strategy, which Barendregt [3, Chapter 3] credits to Tait and Martin-Löf, using the relational approach as used by Pfenning [29]. It relies on defining *parallel* reductions, \Rightarrow , which can reduce all redexes visible in the term in a single step. The overall proof follows closely the other presentations so we skip much of the proof. Figure 12 shows the definition of the parallel reduction rule.

LEMMA 12 (SUBSTITUTION FOR REDUCTION).

If $e_1 \Rightarrow e'_1$ and $e_2 \Rightarrow e'_2$ then $e_1[e_2/x] \Rightarrow e'_1[e'_2/x]$

PROOF. By induction on $e_1 \Rightarrow e'_1$. □

LEMMA 13 (DIAMOND PROPERTY).

If $e \Rightarrow e_l$ and $e \Rightarrow e_r$, then there exists an e_m such that $e_l \Rightarrow e_m$ and $e_r \Rightarrow e_m$.

PROOF. The proof follows by induction on $e \Rightarrow e_l$ and $e \Rightarrow e_r$.

We show only a few subcases.

- Case $e_l = e o r e_r = e$: Trivial.

1735 • Case $\frac{e_1 \Rightarrow e_{l1} \quad e_2 \Rightarrow e_{l2} \quad \tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau_{l1} \quad \tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{l2}}{((\lambda x.e_1) : (x:\tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \Rightarrow (e_{l1} : \tau_{l2})[(e_{l2} : \tau_{l1})/x]}$
 1736
 1737 Then we consider the possible cases for $((\lambda x.e_1) : (x:\tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \Rightarrow e_r$:

1738 $\frac{((\lambda x.e_1) : (x:\tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) \Rightarrow e_{r1} \quad e_2 \Rightarrow e_{r2}}{\bullet}$
 1739
 1740 $((\lambda x.e_1) : (x:\tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \Rightarrow e_{r1} e_{r2}$
 1741 By inversion we can refine this to:

1742 $\frac{e_1 \Rightarrow e_{r1} \quad e_2 \Rightarrow e_{r2} \quad \tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau_{r1} \quad \tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{r2}}{((\lambda x.e_1) : (x:\tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \Rightarrow ((\lambda x.e_{r1}) : (x:\tau_{r1}) \rightarrow \tau_{r2}) e_{r2}}$
 1743
 1744 By the i.h. we derive the following:

1745 - $e_{l1} \Rightarrow e_{m1}$ and $e_{r1} \Rightarrow e_{m1}$ [From $e_1 \Rightarrow e_{l1}$ and $e_1 \Rightarrow e_{r1}$]
 1746 - $e_{l2} \Rightarrow e_{m2}$ and $e_{r2} \Rightarrow e_{m2}$ [From $e_2 \Rightarrow e_{l2}$ and $e_2 \Rightarrow e_{r2}$]
 1747 - $\tau_{l1} \Rightarrow \tau_{m1}$ and $\tau_{r1} \Rightarrow \tau_{m1}$ [From $\tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau_{l1}$ and $\tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau_{r1}$]
 1748 - $\tau_{l2} \Rightarrow \tau_{m2}$ and $\tau_{r2} \Rightarrow \tau_{m2}$ [From $\tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{l2}$ and $\tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{r2}$]

1749 The common term we're targeting is $e_m = (e_{m1} : \tau_{m2})[(e_{m2} : \tau_{m1})/x]$.

1750 For the left side we can derive $(e_{l1} : \tau_{l2}) \Rightarrow (e_{m1} : \tau_{m2})$ and $(e_{l2} : \tau_{l1}) \Rightarrow (e_{m2} : \tau_{m1})$.

1751 By application of Lemma 12, we then get:

1752 $(e_{l1} : \tau_{l2})[(e_{l2} : \tau_{l1})/x] \Rightarrow e_m$

1753 And for the right side we can derive $((\lambda x.e_{r1}) : (x:\tau_{r1}) \rightarrow \tau_{r2}) e_{r2} \Rightarrow e_m$.

1754 $\frac{e_1 \Rightarrow e_{r1} \quad e_2 \Rightarrow e_{r2} \quad \tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau_{r1} \quad \tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{r2}}{\bullet}$
 1755 $((\lambda x.e_1) : (x:\tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \Rightarrow (e_{r1} : \tau_{r2})[(e_{r2} : \tau_{r1})/x]$
 1756
 1757 By the i.h. we derive again the following:

1758 - $e_{l1} \Rightarrow e_{m1}$ and $e_{r1} \Rightarrow e_{m1}$ [From $e_1 \Rightarrow e_{l1}$ and $e_1 \Rightarrow e_{r1}$]
 1759 - $e_{l2} \Rightarrow e_{m2}$ and $e_{r2} \Rightarrow e_{m2}$ [From $e_2 \Rightarrow e_{l2}$ and $e_2 \Rightarrow e_{r2}$]
 1760 - $\tau_{l1} \Rightarrow \tau_{m1}$ and $\tau_{r1} \Rightarrow \tau_{m1}$ [From $\tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau_{l1}$ and $\tau_1 \Rightarrow \tau_{r1}$]
 1761 - $\tau_{l2} \Rightarrow \tau_{m2}$ and $\tau_{r2} \Rightarrow \tau_{m2}$ [From $\tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{l2}$ and $\tau_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{r2}$]

1762 Like last time, the common term we're targeting is $e_m = (e_{m1} : \tau_{m2})[(e_{m2} : \tau_{m1})/x]$.

1763 The left is identical as the last subcase. The right side is identical to the left side.

1764 The other cases follow the same pattern. □

1765 LEMMA 3 (CONFLUENCE).

1766 If $e \rightsquigarrow^* e_l$ and $e \rightsquigarrow^* e_r$, then there exists an e_m such that $e_l \rightsquigarrow^* e_m$ and $e_r \rightsquigarrow^* e_m$.

1767 PROOF. The proof proceeds by using Lemma 13 together with the usual strip lemma to lift
 1768 the diamond property of \Rightarrow to that of \Rightarrow^* and then finishes with side lemmas showing the
 1769 equivalence between \rightsquigarrow^* and \Rightarrow^* . □

1770 A.2 Proof of Lemma 7: Subject reduction

1771 LEMMA 6 (STABILITY OF TYPING).

1772 If $\vdash \Gamma'$ and $\Gamma \simeq \Gamma'$, then

- 1773 • If $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$, and $\Gamma \vdash \tau' \Rightarrow s$, and $\tau \simeq \tau'$ then $\Gamma' \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau'$
- 1774 • If $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma' \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'$.

1775 PROOF. By induction on the typing derivation of e . For SORT, it's immediate. For RED_C
 1776 and CONV, we can use the induction hypothesis together with the transitivity of \simeq . For RED_S
 1777 we use the induction hypothesis together with the confluence. For ANN, by induction we can

1778

1786 get $\Gamma' \vdash \tau \Rightarrow \tau_\tau$ and $s \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_\tau$, from this we know τ_τ is still a sort, so we can conclude using
 1787 induction on the second premise and the use of the ANN rule. For VAR, we get a new type τ'
 1788 for x as well as $\tau \simeq \tau'$ from $\Gamma \simeq \Gamma'$, from this equality we can use the $\tau' \rightsquigarrow^* \tau''$ in a RED_S
 1789 and the $\tau \rightsquigarrow^* \tau''$ to conclude. For PI, we use the induction hypothesis, as we did for ANN.
 1790 For LAM, from $\tau' \simeq (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2$, we know τ' must be reducible to the form $(x : \tau'_1) \rightarrow \tau'_2$
 1791 with $\tau_1 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'_1$ and $\tau_2 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_2$, so we can use induction to get $\Gamma' \vdash \lambda x.e \Leftarrow ((x : \tau'_1) \rightarrow \tau'_2)$
 1792 and then use RED_C to get $\Gamma' \vdash \lambda x.e \Leftarrow \tau'$. For APP, by i.h. the new type of the first premise
 1793 is of the form $(x : \tau'_1) \rightarrow \tau'_2$, with $\tau_1 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'_1$ and $\tau_2 \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_2$, so we can finish after using i.h. on
 1794 the second premise.
 1795

1796 For all the other rules, the proof proceeds in the same way: use induction on the premises
 1797 with insertion of RED_C for checking conclusions. \square
 1798

1799 **LEMMA 7 (SUBJECT REDUCTION).**
 1800

1801 *Given $e \rightsquigarrow e'$, if $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma \vdash e' \Leftarrow \tau$,*
 1802 *and if $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ then $\Gamma \vdash e' \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'$.*
 1803

1804 **PROOF.** By induction on the typing derivation of e . If $e \rightsquigarrow e'$ uses the congruence rule, we
 1805 can use the induction hypothesis sometimes combined with Lemma 6. We show only some
 1806 cases.
 1807

1808 • **Case SORT:** The only possible reduction is $\mathcal{U}_\ell \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell'}$ and we get $\Gamma \vdash \mathcal{U}_{\ell'} : \mathcal{U}_{(S \ell')}$ and
 1809 $\mathcal{U}_{(S \ell)} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{U}_{(S \ell')}$.
 1810

1811 • **Case CONV:** If the reduction is in the subterm, then by i.h. we have $\Gamma \vdash N' \Rightarrow \tau'_1$ and
 1812 $\tau_1 \simeq \tau'_1$ so we get that $\tau_2 \simeq \tau'_1$ and we can immediately conclude by rebuilding a CONV.
 1813

1814 The other possible reduction is $\llbracket (e : \tau_e) \rrbracket \rightsquigarrow e$. We have $\Gamma \vdash (e : \tau_e) \Leftarrow \tau'$ and
 1815 $\Gamma \vdash (e : \tau_e) \Rightarrow \tau_h$ (and $\tau_h \simeq \tau'$), and we know this can come only from a sequence of rules
 1816 that starts with an ANN that has $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_e$ as hypothesis, followed by some number of
 1817 RED_S. So we can combine the $\tau_e \rightsquigarrow^* \dots \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_h$ with the $\tau_h \simeq \tau'$ to get $\tau_e \simeq \tau'$ and conclude
 1818 with the use of Lemma 6.
 1819

1820 • **Case APP:** If the reduction happens within e_2 , then the i.h. gives us that $\Gamma \vdash e'_2 \Rightarrow \tau_1$
 1821 so we can rebuild an APP that gives us $\Gamma \vdash e_1 e'_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2[e'_2/x]$ and we know that
 1822 $\tau_2[e_2/x] \rightsquigarrow^* \tau_2[e'_2/x]$.
 1823

1824 If the reduction happens within e_1 , then the i.h. gives us that $\Gamma \vdash e'_1 \Rightarrow \tau_f$ and
 1825 $(x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \simeq \tau_f$ and hence $\tau_f \rightsquigarrow^* (x : \tau'_1) \rightarrow \tau'_2$. We can combine RED_S on the first
 1826 hypothesis with Lemma 6 on the second hypothesis to rebuild an APP that gives us $\Gamma \vdash$
 1827 $e'_1 e_2 \Rightarrow \tau'_2[e_2/x]$ and we know that $\tau_2[e_2/x] \rightsquigarrow^* \tau'_2[e_2/x]$.
 1828

1829 Finally the reduction can be β , i.e. $((\lambda x.e_1) : (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \rightsquigarrow (e_1 : \tau_2)[(e_2 : \tau_1)/x]$.
 1830 As for CONV, we know that the first premise comes from a LAM rule with a premise of
 1831 $\Gamma, x : \tau'_1 \vdash e_1 \Leftarrow \tau'_2$, followed by some number of RED_C followed by an ANN followed by some
 1832 number of RED_S. By Lemma 3 we have that $\tau_1 \simeq \tau'_1$ and $\tau_2 \simeq \tau'_2$. Lemma 6 then gives us that
 1833 $\Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash e_1 \Leftarrow \tau_2$, after which Lemma 4 gives us $\Gamma \vdash e_1[(e_2 : \tau_1)/x] \Leftarrow \tau_2[(e_2 : \tau_1)/x]$.
 1834 Together with the premise that $\Gamma \vdash e_2 \Leftarrow \tau_1$ we conclude that indeed $\Gamma \vdash (e_1 : \tau_2)[(e_2 :$
 1835 $\tau_1)/x] \Rightarrow \tau_2[(e_2 : \tau_1)/x]$. \square
 1836

A.3 Proof of Lemma 9: Erasure soundness

LEMMA 14 (WEAK HEAD PROGRESS).

If $\bullet \vdash e : \tau$ then one of those holds:

- $\tau \simeq (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2$ and $e = \lambda x.e'$ (only if $\bullet \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$).
- $\tau \simeq \langle x_1 : \tau_1, \dots, x_n : \tau_n \rangle$ and $e = \langle e_1, \dots, e_n \rangle$ (only if $\bullet \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$).
- $\tau \simeq \exists x : \tau_1. \tau_2$ and $e = \langle e_1; e_2 \rangle$ (only if $\bullet \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$).
- $\tau \simeq \exists l. \tau$ and $e = \langle \ell; e' \rangle$ (only if $\bullet \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$).
- $\tau \simeq \text{Eq } e_1 e_2$, $e = \text{refl}$, and $e_1 \simeq e_2$ (only if $\bullet \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$).
- $\tau \simeq Q e_n$ and either $e = \text{Qin}[e'_n] e_v$ or $e = \text{Qn}[e'_n] e_v$.
- $\tau \simeq \mathcal{U}_S \ell$ and
- $e = (e' : \tau')$.
- $e \rightsquigarrow e'$ where the evaluation step uses neither the rule: $\text{Qin}[e_n] e \rightsquigarrow \text{Qn}[e_n] (e_n e)$ nor any evaluation under a binder, i.e. none of the following evaluation contexts:
 $\lambda x.E$, $\text{let } \langle x_1; x_2 \rangle = e \text{ in } E$, $\text{let } \langle l; x \rangle = e \text{ in } E$,
 $\text{letcast}[e_m, e_ =] x = e_1 \text{ in } E$, $\text{let}[e_ =] \text{Qin } x = e_1 \text{ in } E$.

PROOF. By induction on the typing derivation.

The VAR case is impossible because of the empty context. The SORT, LAM, and PI cases are trivially true. For the RED_C, RED_S, and CONV cases, we can simply appeal to the induction hypothesis.

For the APP rule, we first use the induction hypothesis on the function subterm e_f . If that returns a reduction step, then we use the congruence rule to return a corresponding reduction step. If not, it can only return $e_f = (e'_f : \tau')$, so we apply the induction hypothesis again on e'_f . If that returns a reduction step, we conclude with a step using the congruence rule, if it returns $e'_f = (e''_f : \tau')$, we conclude with a corresponding reduction step, and otherwise it has to return $e'_f = \lambda x.e_b$ so we can conclude with a β -reduction step.

The other cases all follow the same patterns. □

LEMMA 9 (ERASURE SOUNDNESS).

If $\bullet \vdash e_1 : \tau$ and $|e_1| \xrightarrow{e} e_2$, then

there exists an e_3 such that $\bullet \vdash e_3 \Leftarrow \tau$ and $e_1 \simeq e_3$ and $|e_3| = e_2$.

PROOF. To reduce the set of cases to consider we start by reducing e_1 by any step that does not affect the erasure: $e_1 \rightsquigarrow e'_1 \wedge |e_1| = |e'_1|$. Assuming strong normalization, there can be only a finite number of such steps.

After that, we proceed by induction on $\bullet \vdash e_1 : \tau$ and $|e_1| \xrightarrow{e} e_2$.

We start by eliminating many trivially impossible cases: the empty context lets us eliminate VAR and because their erasure does not match any reduction rule we can eliminate the constructor and introduction rules SORT, PI and LAM, Σ , \exists , EQ, REFL, and Q.

For rules where the erasure of the term is identical to the erasure of a specific subterm, we can use the induction hypothesis since that subterm is always typed in the same context as the term itself. These are: RED_C, RED_S, CONV, ANN, PACK, U-PACK, QIN, and QN.

For the TUP rule, the \xrightarrow{e} step necessarily used a congruence rule, and the subterm which is reduced is necessarily typed in the empty context, so we can use the induction hypothesis on it and then use the congruence rule of \rightsquigarrow to conclude.

1888 For the APP rule, we have that $e_1 = e_f e_a$ and $\bullet \vdash e_f \Rightarrow (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2$. If the $\overset{e}{\sim}$ step
 1889 used a congruence rule, then the same applies as for TUP. If the $\overset{e}{\sim}$ step used the β -reduction
 1890 rule, then $|e_f| = \lambda x.e'_b$, and the only e_f possible are $\lambda x.e_b$ and $(\lambda x.e_b : (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2)$,
 1891 which both let us use $e_3 = e_b[e_2/x]$.

1892 The PROJ, OPEN, U-OPEN, and LETCAST rules proceed like the APP rule.

1893 The QOUT rule also proceeds similarly when the $\overset{e}{\sim}$ step used a congruence rule. But
 1894 when the $\overset{e}{\sim}$ step used the let-reduction rule, there is a twist. From the typing of e_1 we
 1895 know that $e_1 = \text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = e_v \text{ in } e_b$ and $\Gamma \vdash e_v \Rightarrow \text{Q } e_n$, and from the reduction step
 1896 we know that $|e_1| = \text{let } x = v \text{ in } e$ and $|e_v| = v$. Because we have performed all the erasable
 1897 reductions, there are only 2 possible shapes for e_v : either $\text{Qin}[e_n] e_i$ or $\text{Qn}[e_n] e_i$. When
 1898 $e_v = \text{Qn}[e_n] e_i$, we can use the corresponding reduction step to get $e_3 = e_b[e_i/x]$, but when
 1899 $e_v = \text{Qin}[e_n] e_i$, the reduction proceeds in two steps:

1900
$$\text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = \text{Qin}[e_n] e_i \text{ in } e_b \rightsquigarrow \text{let}[e_=_] \text{Qin } x = \text{Qn}[e_n] e_n e_i \text{ in } e_b \rightsquigarrow e_b[e_n e_i/x]$$

1901 but we need something that erases to $|e_b|[[|e_v|/x]]$!

1902 Luckily, we know that $\bullet \vdash e_=_ e_i \Leftarrow \text{Eq } e_b[e_i/x] e_b[e_n e_i/x]$. Assuming again strong
 1903 normalization, we can reduce $e_=_ e_i$ to a normal form $e'_=_$. Lemma 14 in turn tells us that $e'_=_$
 1904 can be only refl, which gives us the proof of $e_b[e_i/x] \simeq e_b[e_n e_i/x]$ that we needed to conclude.
 1905 \square

1906 A.4 Proof of Lemma 10: Substitution commutes

1907 LEMMA 10 (SUBSTITUTION COMMUTES).

1908 Given $\Gamma = \Gamma_1, x : \tau_x, \Gamma_2$ and $\Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1$ and $\Gamma_1 \vdash e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_x$ and $e'_2 = \llbracket \Gamma_1 \vdash e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_x \rrbracket$:
 1909 for all $e_s = \llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2[e_2/x] \vdash e_1[e_2/x] : \tau_1[e_2/x] \rrbracket$
 1910 there exists an $e_c = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rrbracket$ such that $e_s \simeq e_c[e'_2/x]$.

1911 PROOF. The induction is done on the typing derivation of e_1 .

1912 • Case SORT, $e_1 = \mathcal{U}_\ell$, trivial: $\llbracket \mathcal{U}_\ell \rrbracket [e'_2/x] = \mathcal{U}_\ell[e'_2/x] = \mathcal{U}_\ell = \llbracket \mathcal{U}_\ell \rrbracket = \llbracket \mathcal{U}_\ell[e_2/x] \rrbracket$

1913 • Case VAR, $e_1 = x_v$:
 1914 if $x \neq x_v$ then $\llbracket x_v \rrbracket [e'_2/x] = x_v[e'_2/x] = x_v = \llbracket x_v \rrbracket = \llbracket x_v[e_2/x] \rrbracket$

1915 otherwise $\llbracket x \rrbracket [e'_2/x] = x[e'_2/x] = e'_2 = \llbracket x[e_2/x] \rrbracket$

1916 • Case CONV, $e_1 = \lfloor N \rfloor$ and $\Gamma \vdash N \Rightarrow \tau_2$:
 1917 By i.h. we have that for all $e'_s = \llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2[e_2/x] \vdash N[e_2/x] \Rightarrow \tau_2[e_2/x] \rrbracket$

1918 there exists an $e'_c = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash N \Rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket$ such that $e'_s \simeq e'_c[e'_2/x]$. And since $\llbracket \lfloor N \rfloor \rrbracket = \llbracket N \rrbracket$,
 1919 for all e_s that $\llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2[e_2/x] \vdash \lfloor N \rfloor[e_2/x] \Rightarrow \tau_2[e_2/x] \rrbracket$ may return, there exist the same
 1920 corresponding $e_c = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash \lfloor N \rfloor \Rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket$ such that $e_s \simeq e_c[e'_2/x]$.

1921 • Case RED, ANN, PI, APP, Same approach: for any e_s , we can extract the subterms of the
 1922 nested calls to $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ and use the i.h. on them, after which we can conclude by rebuilding an
 1923 e_c that is shown to be equal using the definition of the substitution and the congruence of
 1924 definitional equality.

1925 \square

1939 • Case LAM, $e_1 = \lambda x_a.e$, more specifically:

1940

1941

1942

1943

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_a : \tau_a \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_r}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x_a.e \Leftarrow ((x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r)}$$

1944 We also know that

1945

1946

1947

1948

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \tau_a \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_a} \quad \Gamma, x_a : \tau_a \vdash \tau_r \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_r} \quad \ell = \max(\ell_a, \ell_r)}{\Gamma \vdash (x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_\ell}$$

1949 and thus

1950

1951

1952

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1957

$$\frac{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, x_a : \tau_a[e'_2/x] \vdash e[e'_2/x] \Leftarrow \tau_r[e'_2/x]}{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \lambda x_a.e[e'_2/x] \Leftarrow ((x_a : \tau_a[e'_2/x]) \rightarrow \tau_r[e'_2/x])}$$

By induction we have

$$\forall e'_s = \llbracket e[e_2/x] \rrbracket . \exists e'_c = \llbracket e \rrbracket . e'_s = e'_c[e'_2/x]$$

1958 and

1959

1960

1961

1962 and

1963

1964

1965

$$\forall \tau_{as} = \llbracket \tau_a[e_2/x] \rrbracket . \exists \tau_{ac} = \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket . \tau_{as} \simeq \tau_{ac}[e'_2/x]$$

$$\forall \tau_{rs} = \llbracket \tau_r[e_2/x] \rrbracket / \exists \tau_{rc} = \llbracket \tau_r \rrbracket . \tau_{rs} \simeq \tau_{rc}[e'_2/x]$$

1966

We're trying to prove $\forall e_s = \llbracket (\lambda x_a.e)[e_2/x] \rrbracket . \exists e_c = \llbracket \lambda x_a.e \rrbracket . e_s \simeq e_c[e'_2/x]$.

1967

For the benefit of clarity, we consider only the case where `tfv` just returns all the vars, so

1968

$\Gamma' = \Gamma$ and $\vec{x} = \text{Dom}(\Gamma)$.

1969

$\llbracket (\lambda x_a.e)[e_2/x] \rrbracket$, i.e. e_s , must expand to:

1970

1971

1972

1973

1974

1975

1976

1977

1978

1979

1980

`Qin[norm clo]`

$(\langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \rrbracket \rrbracket; \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_\pm \rangle . \text{body} \rangle \rangle : \text{clo})$

where $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash \langle \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \rangle \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_\ell$

Compute the universe level ℓ

$\text{clo} = \text{clotype } \tau_{as} \ x_a . \tau_{rs}$

$\vec{x} = \text{Dom}(\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2)$

$f_m = \lambda \langle \vec{x} \rangle . (x_a : \tau_{as}) \rightarrow \tau_{rs}$

The motive of the cast

$\text{body} = \text{letcast}[f_m, x_\pm] \ x_a = x'_a \ \text{in}$

$\text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = x_e \ \text{in } e'_s$

1981

where we used τ_{as} for $\llbracket \tau_a[e_2/x] \rrbracket$, τ_{rs} for $\llbracket \tau_r[e_2/x] \rrbracket$, and e'_s for $\llbracket e[e_2/x] \rrbracket$. The normalization argument passed to `Qin` reduces to:

1982

1983

1984

1985

1986

1987

1988

1989

cnorm

$= \text{norm clo}$

$= (\lambda c . \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \text{call } c \ x_a \rangle \rangle >>$

$: \text{clo} \rightarrow \text{clo}$

so the whole Qin reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Qin}[cnorm] \\
& (\langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \rrbracket \rrbracket; \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body \rangle \rangle \rangle : clo) \\
& \simeq \{ \text{Reduce Qin to Qn} \} \\
& \text{Qn}[cnorm] \\
& ((\lambda c. \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \text{call } c \ x_a \rangle \rangle \rangle) \\
& (\langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \rrbracket \rrbracket; \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body \rangle \rangle \rangle : clo)) \\
& \simeq \{ \beta\text{-reduce} \} \\
& \text{Qn}[cnorm] \\
& (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \text{call} \left(\begin{array}{l} \langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \rrbracket \rrbracket; \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body \rangle \rangle \rangle \\ : clo \end{array} \right) x_a \rangle \rangle \rangle) \\
& = \{ \text{Inline+reduce: call } c \ x = \text{let } \langle l; \langle t; \langle env, code \rangle \rangle \rangle = c \text{ in } code \langle env, x, refl \rangle \} \\
& \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . ((\lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body) \langle \vec{x} \rangle, x_a, refl)) \rangle \rangle \rangle) \\
& \simeq \{ \text{Reduce further} \} \\
& \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . (body[\langle \vec{x} \rangle / x_e, x_a / x'_a, refl / x_=]) \rangle \rangle \rangle) \\
& = \{ \text{Expose } body \} \\
& \text{Qn}[cnorm] \\
& (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{letcast}[f_m, x_=] \ x_a = x'_a \text{ in} \\ \text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = x_e \text{ in } e'_s \end{array} \right) [\langle \vec{x} \rangle / x_e, x_a / x'_a, refl / x_=] \rangle \rangle \rangle) \\
& = \{ \text{Substitute into } body \} \\
& \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{letcast}[f_m, refl] \ x_a = x_a \text{ in} \\ \text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = \langle \vec{x} \rangle \text{ in } e'_s \end{array} \right) \rangle \rangle \rangle) \\
& = \{ \text{Reduce} \} \\
& \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle \rangle)
\end{aligned}$$

Now for $\llbracket \lambda x_a . e \rrbracket [e'_2 / x]$, it expands to:

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\text{Qin}[clo']) \\
& (\langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \rrbracket; \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body \rangle \rangle \rangle : clo') [e'_2 / x] \\
& \text{where } \Gamma \vdash \langle \Gamma \rangle \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_\ell \quad \text{Compute the universe level } \ell \\
& \quad clo' = \text{clotype } \tau_{ac} \ x_a . \tau_{rc} \\
& \quad \vec{x} = \text{Dom}(\Gamma) \\
& \quad f_m = \lambda \langle \vec{x} \rangle . (x_a : \tau_{ac}) \rightarrow \tau_{rc} \quad \text{The motive of the cast} \\
& \quad body = \text{letcast}[f_m, x_=] \ x_a = x'_a \text{ in} \\
& \quad \quad \text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = x_e \text{ in } e'_c
\end{aligned}$$

where we used τ_{ac} for $\llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket$, τ_{rc} for $\llbracket \tau_r \rrbracket$, and e'_c for $\llbracket e \rrbracket$. After distributing the substitution to both arguments of Qin, the normalization argument passed to Qin reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned}
& cnorm' \\
& = (\text{norm } clo') [e'_2 / x] \\
& = (\lambda c. \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \text{call } c \ x_a \rangle \rangle \rangle \\
& \quad : (clo' \rightarrow clo') [e'_2 / x])
\end{aligned}$$

2041 The whole Qin reduces as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
2042 & \text{Qin}[cnorm'] \\
2043 & \left(\langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \rangle; \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle [e'_2/x], \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_{=} \rangle . body[e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle \right) \\
2044 & \quad : clo'[e'_2/x] \\
2045 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce Qin to Qn} \} \\
2046 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] \\
2047 & \left((\lambda c. \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . call\ c\ x_a \rangle \rangle) \right) \\
2048 & \quad (\langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \rangle; \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle [e'_2/x], \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_{=} \rangle . body[e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2049 & \quad : clo'[e'_2/x]) \\
2050 & \simeq \{ \beta\text{-reduce} \} \\
2051 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \\
2052 & \quad call \left(\langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \rangle; \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle [e'_2/x], \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_{=} \rangle . body[e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle \right) x_a \rangle \rangle) \\
2053 & \simeq \{ \text{Inline+reduce: call } c\ x = \text{let } \langle l; \langle t; \langle env, code \rangle \rangle = c \text{ in } code \langle env, x, refl \rangle \} \\
2054 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \\
2055 & \quad ((\lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_{=} \rangle . body[e'_2/x]) \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle [e'_2/x], x_a, refl \rangle) \rangle \rangle) \\
2056 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce further} \} \\
2057 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \\
2058 & \quad (body[e'_2/x][\langle \vec{x} \rangle [e'_2/x]/x_e, x_a/x'_a, refl/x_{=}] \rangle \rangle) \\
2059 & \simeq \{ \text{Swap the two substitutions} \} \\
2060 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \\
2061 & \quad (body[\langle \vec{x} \rangle / x_e, x_a/x'_a, refl/x_{=}] [e'_2/x]) \rangle \rangle) \\
2062 & \simeq \{ \text{Expose body} \} \\
2063 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \\
2064 & \quad \left(\text{letcast}[f_m, x_{=}] x_a = x'_a \text{ in } [\langle \vec{x} \rangle / x_e, x_a/x'_a, refl/x_{=}] [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2065 & \quad \left(\text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = x_e \text{ in } \llbracket e \rrbracket \right) \right) \\
2066 & \simeq \{ \text{Substitute into body} \} \\
2067 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \left(\text{letcast}[f_m, refl] x_a = x_a \text{ in } \right) [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2068 & \quad \left(\text{let } \langle \vec{x} \rangle = \langle \vec{x} \rangle \text{ in } \llbracket e \rrbracket \right) \right) \\
2069 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce} \} \\
2070 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \llbracket e \rrbracket [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2071 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce} \} \\
2072 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \llbracket e \rrbracket [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2073 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce} \} \\
2074 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \llbracket e \rrbracket [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2075 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce} \} \\
2076 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \llbracket e \rrbracket [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2077 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce} \} \\
2078 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \llbracket e \rrbracket [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2079 & \simeq \{ \text{Reduce} \} \\
2080 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_c [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2081 & \simeq \\
2082 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2083 & \simeq \\
2084 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2085 & \simeq \\
2086 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2087 & \simeq \\
2088 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2089 & \simeq \\
2090 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2091 & \simeq \\
\end{aligned}$$

2076 Note that the \vec{x} of captured variables in the two developments are not identical: in one
2077 it includes x and in the other it doesn't, but the Qin normalization successfully hides the
2078 difference.

2079 So, now we need to show:

$$\begin{aligned}
2080 & \text{Qn}[cnorm'] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_c [e'_2/x] \rangle \rangle) \\
2081 & \simeq \\
2082 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2083 & \simeq \\
2084 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2085 & \simeq \\
2086 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2087 & \simeq \\
2088 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2089 & \simeq \\
2090 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
2091 & \simeq \\
\end{aligned}$$

2085 We already know that $e'_c [e'_2/x] \simeq e'_s$, so we only need to show $cnorm \simeq cnorm'$:

$$\begin{aligned}
2086 & cnorm = (\lambda c. \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . call\ c\ x_a \rangle \rangle) \\
2087 & \quad : clo \rightarrow clo \\
2088 & cnorm' = (\lambda c. \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . call\ c\ x_a \rangle \rangle) \\
2089 & \quad : (clo' \rightarrow clo') [e'_2/x] \\
2090 & \simeq \\
2091 & \text{Qn}[cnorm] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e'_s \rangle \rangle) \\
\end{aligned}$$

2092 so we just need to show:

$$2093 \quad clo \simeq clo'[e'_2/x]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2094 \quad & \\
2095 \quad & clo \\
2096 \quad & = \{ \text{by definition} \} \\
2097 \quad & \exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle env : t, \\
2098 \quad & \quad code : \langle x_e : t, x : \tau_{as}, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rightarrow \tau_{rs} \rangle \\
2099 \quad & \simeq \{ \text{by induction} \} \\
2100 \quad & \exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle env : t, \\
2101 \quad & \quad code : \langle x_e : t, x : \tau_{ac}[e'_2/x], p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rightarrow \tau_{rc}[e'_2/x] \rangle \\
2102 \quad & = \{ \text{by hoisting\&consolidating the substitutions} \} \\
2103 \quad & (\exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle env : t, \\
2104 \quad & \quad code : \langle x_e : t, x : \tau_{ac}, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rightarrow \tau_{rc} \rangle)[e'_2/x] \\
2105 \quad & = \{ \text{by definition} \} \\
2106 \quad & (clo')[e'_2/x] \\
2107 \quad & \\
2108 \quad &
\end{aligned}$$

2109 \square

2111 **A.5 Proof of Theorem 1: Computational soundness**

2112 **THEOREM 1 (COMPUTATIONAL SOUNDNESS).**

2113 *If $\Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1$ and $\Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2$ and $\Gamma_1 \simeq \Gamma_2$ and $e_1 \simeq e_2$ and $\tau_1 \simeq \tau_2$,*
2114 *then $\llbracket \Gamma_1 \vdash e_1 : \tau_1 \rrbracket \simeq \llbracket \Gamma_2 \vdash e_2 : \tau_2 \rrbracket$.*

2116 **PROOF.** By induction on $e_1 \simeq e_2$ we can reduce the problem to either $e_1 = e_2$ or $e_1 \rightsquigarrow e_2$.
2117 Then we proceed by induction on the typing derivation of e_1 :

- 2119 • Case SORT: Immediate.
- 2120 • Case RED: By the induction hypothesis.
- 2121 • Case CONV, ANN: Again, since $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ just recurses on the subterm, we can conclude by using
2122 the i.h. even when $\llbracket (e : \tau) \rrbracket \rightsquigarrow e$.
- 2123 • Case Pr: By induction on the two subterms.
- 2124 • Case LAM: By the i.h. we know that both τ'_a will be \simeq , both τ'_r will be \simeq , and similarly both
2125 recursions on e will return bodies that are \simeq . And if we assume that tfv returns the same \vec{x}_f ,
2126 then it's clear that both sides return code that is \simeq since each pairs of subterms are \simeq . If the
2127 two \vec{x}_f are not equal, on the other hand, we need to look closer.

2128 The returned code is of the form $\text{Qin}[\text{norm } clo] \dots$ And as we've just seen in the previous
2129 proof, these reduce to just $\text{Qn}[\text{norm } clo] (\langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . e \rangle \rangle \rangle)$ where the effect
2130 of \vec{x}_f have disappeared, so the equality is preserved.

- 2131 • Case APP: There are two subcases here, depending on whether $e_1 \rightsquigarrow e_2$ is a β reduction or
2132 instead uses a congruence rule. In the case of a congruence rule, then we can use the i.h. to
2133 show that all the pairs of subterms are \simeq and hence so are the two results.

2134 As for the the case of $((\lambda x. e_1) : (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2) e_2 \rightsquigarrow (e_1 : \tau_2)[(e_2 : \tau_1)/x]$, we need to
2135 show $\llbracket ((\lambda x_a. e_1) : (x : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r) e_2 \rrbracket \simeq \llbracket (e_1 : \tau_r)[(e_2 : \tau_a)/x_a] \rrbracket$:

2140
2141
2142

2143 $\llbracket ((\lambda x_a. e_1) : (x : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r) e_2 \rrbracket$
 2144 = {By definition of $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ for applications}
 2145 let[refl] Qin $c = \llbracket ((\lambda x_a. e_1) : (x : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r) \rrbracket$ in call $c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket$
 2146 = {By definition of $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ for type annotations}
 2147 let[refl] Qin $c = (\llbracket \lambda x_a. e_1 \rrbracket : \llbracket (x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r \rrbracket)$ in call $c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket$
 2148 = { By definition of $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ for λ }
 2149 let[refl] Qin $c = (\text{Qin}[\text{norm } clo]$
 2150 $\quad \langle \ell; \langle \llbracket \Gamma' \rrbracket \rangle; \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body \rangle \rangle \rangle$
 2151 $\quad : clo$
 2152 $\quad : \llbracket (x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r \rrbracket)$
 2153
 2154 in call $c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket$
 2155 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \text{Reduce Qin to Qn} \}$
 2156 let[refl] Qin $c = (\text{Qn}[\text{norm } clo]$
 2157 $\quad \langle \langle \ell. \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . \text{call } c \ x_a \rangle \rangle \rangle \rangle$
 2158 $\quad \langle \ell; \langle \langle \llbracket \Gamma' \rrbracket \rangle; \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body \rangle \rangle \rangle$
 2159 $\quad : \text{clotype } \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket \ x_a. \llbracket \tau_r \rrbracket)$
 2160 $\quad : \llbracket (x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r \rrbracket)$
 2161
 2162 in call $c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket$
 2163 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \beta\text{-reduce, then inline+reduce call} \}$
 2164 let[refl] Qin $c = (\text{Qn}[\text{norm } clo]$
 2165 $\quad \langle \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . (\lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body) \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle, x_a, \text{refl} \rangle \rangle \rangle \rangle$
 2166 $\quad : \text{clotype } \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket \ x_a. \llbracket \tau_r \rrbracket)$
 2167 $\quad : \llbracket (x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r \rrbracket)$
 2168
 2169 in call $c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket$
 2170 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \text{Reduce the quotient then inline call} \}$
 2171 let $\langle l; \langle t; \langle env, code \rangle \rangle \rangle$
 2172 $\quad = \langle \langle 1; \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . (\lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body) \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle, x_a, \text{refl} \rangle \rangle \rangle \rangle$
 2173 $\quad : \text{clotype } \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket \ x_a. \llbracket \tau_r \rrbracket)$
 2174 in $code \langle env, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle$
 2175 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \text{Reduce} \}$
 2176 $(\lambda \langle x_e, x_a, p \rangle . (\lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body) \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle, x_a, \text{refl} \rangle) \langle \langle \rangle, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle$
 2177 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \text{Reduce} \}$
 2178 $(\lambda \langle x_e, x'_a, x_= \rangle . body) \langle \langle \vec{x} \rangle, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle$
 2179 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \text{Expand } body, \beta\text{-reduce, and (re)display the type annotations} \}$
 2180 letcast[f_m, refl] $x_a = (\llbracket e_2 \rrbracket : \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket)$ in
 2181 let $\langle \vec{x} \rangle = \langle \vec{x} \rangle$ in $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket$
 2182 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \text{Expand } f_m \}$
 2183 letcast[$(\lambda \langle \vec{x} \rangle . (x_a : \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket) \rightarrow \llbracket \tau_r \rrbracket), \text{refl}$] $x_a = (\llbracket e_2 \rrbracket : \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket)$ in
 2184 let $\langle \vec{x} \rangle = \langle \vec{x} \rangle$ in $\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket$
 2185 $\rightsquigarrow^* \{ \text{Reduce the lets} \}$
 2186 $(\llbracket e_1 \rrbracket : \llbracket \tau_r \rrbracket) [(\llbracket e_2 \rrbracket : \llbracket \tau_a \rrbracket) / x_a]$
 2187 = { By definition of $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ for type annotations }
 2188 $\llbracket (e_1 : \tau_r) \rrbracket [\llbracket (e_2 : \tau_a) \rrbracket / x_a]$
 2189 $\simeq \{ \text{By Lemma 10 plus i.h.} \}$
 2190 $\llbracket (e_1 : \tau_r) \rrbracket [(e_2 : \tau_a) / x_a]$
 2191
 2192
 2193

2194 Note that in the last step, Lemma 10 gives us a specific $e_c = \llbracket (e_1 : \tau_r) \rrbracket$ such that
 2195 $e_c \llbracket \llbracket (e_2 : \tau_a) \rrbracket / x_a \rrbracket \simeq \llbracket (e_1 : \tau_r) \rrbracket \llbracket (e_2 : \tau_a) / x_a \rrbracket$, but by the induction hypothesis we have
 2196 that all possible $\llbracket (e_1 : \tau_r) \rrbracket$ are \simeq between themselves, so the equality holds in general rather
 2197 than only for that specific e_c . \square
 2198

2199 A.6 Proof of Theorem 2: Typing soundness

2200 THEOREM 2 (TYPING SOUNDNESS).

2201 *If $\Gamma \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau$, then $\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \llbracket e \rrbracket \Leftarrow \llbracket \tau \rrbracket$ and*

2202 *if $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$, then $\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \llbracket e \rrbracket \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau' \simeq \llbracket \tau \rrbracket$*

2203
 2204 PROOF. The proof proceeds by induction on the typing derivation. For concision, we will
 2205 often write $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau$ when what we have really is $\Gamma \vdash e \Rightarrow \tau'$ and $\tau \simeq \tau'$.
 2206

2207 • Case VAR, more specifically:

$$2208 \frac{\Gamma(x) = \tau}{2209 \Gamma \vdash x \Rightarrow \tau}$$

2210 The proof is trivial:

$$2211 \frac{2212 \frac{\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket (x) = \llbracket \tau \rrbracket}{2213 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash x \Rightarrow \llbracket \tau \rrbracket}}{2214 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \llbracket x \rrbracket \Rightarrow \llbracket \tau \rrbracket}$$

2215
 2216 • Case APP, more specifically:

$$2217 \frac{\Gamma \vdash e_1 \Rightarrow (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \quad \Gamma \vdash e_2 \Leftarrow \tau_1}{2218 \Gamma \vdash e_1 e_2 \Rightarrow \tau_2 \llbracket (e_2 : \tau_1) / x \rrbracket}$$

2219 Let's call $\tau'_1 = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash \tau_1 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_1} \rrbracket$ and $\tau'_2 = \llbracket \Gamma, x : \tau_1 \vdash \tau_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_2} \rrbracket$.

2220 By induction we have

$$2221 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \llbracket e_1 \rrbracket \Rightarrow \llbracket (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket$$

2222 and

$$2223 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \Leftarrow \tau'_1$$

2224 First we can show that, given an appropriately typed c , call $c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket$ has the expected type τ'_2
 2225 $= \tau'_2 \llbracket \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket : \tau'_1 / x \rrbracket$:
 2226

$$2227 \frac{2228 \frac{\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \Leftarrow \tau'_1}{2229 \frac{\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2, t : \mathcal{U}_l, \text{env} : t, \text{code} : \dots \vdash \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \Leftarrow \tau'_1}{2230 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_l, \text{env} : t, \text{code} : \dots \vdash \langle \text{env}, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle \Leftarrow \langle x_e : t, x : \tau'_1, p : (x_e = \text{env}) \rangle}}{2231 \frac{\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_l, \dots, \text{env} : t, \text{code} : \dots \vdash \text{code} \langle \text{env}, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle \Leftarrow \tau'_2}{2232 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_l, c_2 : \dots \vdash \text{let } \langle \text{env}, \text{code} \rangle = c_2 \text{ in code } \langle \text{env}, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle \Leftarrow \tau'_2}}{2233 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, c_1 : \dots \vdash \text{let } \langle t; \langle \text{env}, \text{code} \rangle \rangle = c_1 \text{ in code } \langle \text{env}, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle \Leftarrow \tau'_2}}{2234 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots \vdash \text{let } \langle l; \langle t; \langle \text{env}, \text{code} \rangle \rangle \rangle = c_1 \text{ in code } \langle \text{env}, \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket, \text{refl} \rangle \Leftarrow \tau'_2}}{2235 \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2 \vdash \text{call } c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket \Leftarrow \tau'_2}$$

2236 Then we can show $\text{refl} : \text{Eq} (\text{call } c \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket) (\text{call } (\text{norm } \text{clo } c) \llbracket e_2 \rrbracket)$ which we will need below
 2237 in the code which extracts the closure from the quotient. The proof is not shown because it
 2238 follows the same pattern as the reductions we've seen in the proof of Theorem 1.
 2239

2240 With that, we can conclude:
 2241
 2242
 2243
 2244

Finally we check the quotiented type:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{2296} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, \dots, x : \tau'_1, \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_l, \dots, c_2 : \langle env : t, code : \dots \rangle \\
\text{2297} \quad \vdash \langle c_2.1, x, refl \rangle \Leftarrow \langle x_e : t, x : \tau'_1, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \\
\text{2298} \\
\text{2299} \quad \hline
\text{2300} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_l, \dots, c_2 : \langle env : t, code : \langle x_e : t, x : \tau'_1, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rangle \rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2301} \quad \vdash c_2.2 \langle c_2.1, x, refl \rangle \Rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2302} \quad \hline
\text{2303} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_l, c_2 : \langle env : t, code : \dots \rangle \\
\text{2304} \quad \vdash \text{let } \langle env, code \rangle = c_2 \text{ in code } \langle env, x, refl \rangle \Rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2305} \quad \hline
\text{2306} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, \dots, c_1 : \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle env : t, code : \dots \rangle \\
\text{2307} \quad \vdash \text{let } \langle t; \langle env, code \rangle \rangle = c_1 \text{ in code } \langle env, x, refl \rangle \Rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2308} \quad \hline
\text{2309} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle env : t, code : \dots \rangle, \dots \\
\text{2310} \quad \vdash \text{let } \langle l; \langle t; \langle env, code \rangle \rangle \rangle = c \text{ in code } \langle env, x, refl \rangle \Rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2311} \quad \hline
\text{2312} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2, \dots \\
\text{2313} \quad \vdash \text{let } \langle l; \langle t; \langle env, code \rangle \rangle \rangle = c \text{ in code } \langle env, x, refl \rangle \Rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2314} \quad \hline
\text{2315} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_1, env : \langle \bullet \rangle, x_e : \langle \bullet \rangle, x : \tau'_1, p : (x_e = env) \\
\text{2316} \quad \vdash \text{call } c \ x \Rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2317} \quad \hline
\text{2318} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_1, env : \langle \bullet \rangle \vdash \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. \text{call } c \ x \\
\text{2319} \quad \Leftarrow \langle x_e : \langle \bullet \rangle, x : \tau'_1, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2320} \quad \hline
\text{2321} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots, t : \mathcal{U}_1 \vdash \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. \text{call } c \ x \rangle \\
\text{2322} \quad \Leftarrow \langle env : \langle \bullet \rangle, code : \langle x_e : \langle \bullet \rangle, x : \tau'_1, p : (x_e = env) \rangle \rangle \rightarrow \tau'_2 \\
\text{2323} \quad \hline
\text{2324} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \dots \vdash \langle \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. \text{call } c \ x \rangle \rangle \\
\text{2325} \quad \Leftarrow \exists l. \exists t : \mathcal{U}_l. \langle env : t, code : \dots \rangle \\
\text{2326} \quad \hline
\text{2327} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, c : \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2 \vdash \langle \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. \text{call } c \ x \rangle \rangle \\
\text{2328} \quad \Leftarrow \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2 \\
\text{2329} \quad \hline
\text{2330} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \lambda c. \langle \langle \bullet \rangle; \langle \langle \rangle, \lambda \langle x_e, x, p \rangle. \text{call } c \ x \rangle \rangle \\
\text{2331} \quad \Leftarrow \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2 \rightarrow \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2 \\
\text{2332} \quad \hline
\text{2333} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \text{norm } (\text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2) \Rightarrow \text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2 \\
\text{2334} \quad \hline
\text{2335} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \text{Q } (\text{norm } (\text{clotype } \tau'_1 x. \tau'_2)) \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_3} \\
\text{2336} \quad \hline
\text{2337} \quad \llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket \vdash \llbracket (x : \tau_1) \rightarrow \tau_2 \rrbracket \Rightarrow \llbracket \mathcal{U}_{\ell_3} \rrbracket
\end{array}$$

• Case LAM, more specifically:

$$\frac{\Gamma, x_a : \tau_a \vdash e \Leftarrow \tau_r}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x_a. e \Leftarrow ((x_a : \tau_a) \rightarrow \tau_r)}$$

Let's call $\tau'_a = \llbracket \Gamma \vdash \tau_a \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_a} \rrbracket$ and $\tau'_r = \llbracket \Gamma, x_a : \tau_a \vdash \tau_r \Rightarrow \mathcal{U}_{\ell_r} \rrbracket$.

By induction hypothesis we have:

$$\llbracket \Gamma \rrbracket, x_a : \tau'_a \vdash \llbracket e \rrbracket \Leftarrow \tau'_r$$

We already confirmed in the previous case that $\text{norm } (\text{clotype } \tau'_a x. \tau'_r)$ is properly typed, so we don't check that again.

The main part is to check the body:

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2398 • Case `CONV`, `RED`, `ANN`: For these cases, the closure conversion does not generate any code,
2399 and it is easy to see that it preserves typing by using the induction hypothesis together with
2400 the Computational soundness Theorem 1. □

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